

MIMS 2.7-8 : War & Government

The Rise and Fall of US Military Dominance¹, from an Art of War perspective, and MIMS Analysis, as well as a short discussion of the history of failures of government programs from antiquity through the Great Enlightenment

A SPACERStm paper²

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

September 2021

Best viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3B6HdJk>

ABSTRACT

There's only one MIMS ever created worse than war, and that's government. As much as people say we need it, the fact is that nothing has killed more people than government policies and programs. Yet, they remain. Furthermore, while war may very occasionally be necessary, it comes at a terrible cost. In this paper the author examines the rise of the world's greatest empire and super power of all time, from the end of World War II to the embarrassing defeats of Vietnam and now Afghanistan and Iraq (War on Terror or WoT). The peak of the Gulf War will also be examined. The role of the NWO and Military Industrial Complex will also be discussed tangentially, but the most effort given to the examination in antiquity of the government MIMS, and disastrous policies and programs which define that which we all know: war and government decrease Human Momentum & Energy more often than aid it.

Keywords: MIMS - War - US Government - Afghanistan - Vietnam - Gulf War - China

¹ The 4th paper of a series on US Strategy/Military

² SPACERS is a secret acronym, but suffice it to say strategy is one of the core aspects to the business, as is analytics.

Introduction	3
MIMS 2.7 - Government	4
Government in Antiquity	8
Enuma Elish	11
Failed Ancient Government Programs	16
Mankind's Quest for the Weapons of the Gods	20
Table 1 - Weapons of the Gods	21
Equation 1: the Food Equation	25
The Tablets of Destiny	26
The Peasantry's Hope for a Holy Grail	26
Government Breeds War	29
List of American Wars since the Civil War	30
The Origins of War	36
MIMS 2.8 - War, the anti-MIMS	39
An Industrial Nation, Steeped in Blood	41
Table 2 - 4 Currents of American Dominance	41
The Rise of The Superpower	43
And to the Republic, For Which it Stands...	45
No Nation that Loves War	45
Winning the First Cold War	46
Ignorance Breeds Arrogance	47
Arrogance Breeds Catastrophe	47
The Three Body Problem	48
World War 3: the Sequel No One Wants	49
How War is the anti-MIMS	52
Conclusion	55
References	57

Introduction

You do not have to go far back in history to find examples of government created crises: Chernobyl, Tiananmen Square, Hong Kong, Darfur, Bosnia, Tibet, Apartheid, Venezuela, Cuba, ISIS, etc... All of these have a basis in the singular but multiform MIMS known as Government. While the names, faces, and shape of government all change, what does not seem to change is the behavior. Wherever people are governing each other, they abuse power, become corrupt, and destroy lives. It's a sad fact, but still a fact.

The largest means (or most obvious perhaps) is through a separate MIMS (or anti-MIMS as we may find out), commonly called "war." There are many kinds of war, however, and we need to distinguish between them a little bit. But what is common between them is that they are destructive, and yet innovative.³ This conundrum will also be explored.

The author wishes to note that there is one common thread between all governments: they exist because of an almost ubiquitous religion which no one seems to question: **the religion of Authority**.

This paradigm is based on multicultural DNA stretching back to antiquity⁴ and the Divine Right to Rule^{5,6}. When we look at ancient [failed] government programs, we will also examine the roots of war, and see that, indeed, the origins of this MIMS hearken back to the Clash of the Titans, and what mankind learned from the new Lord: planet Jupiter.

Figure 1 - The "big G" diagram; credit: author⁷

³ Note reference to MIMS 2.4

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

⁵

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

⁷

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

MIMS 2.7 - Government

The author hypothesizes that this is by far, the worst MIMS ever created. It has surprising EPEMC connections. It does appear, however, to be innocently created. In the earliest days, mankind believed that the tribal chief had a divine responsibility. In some cultures shaman work was divided between a male and female, or belonged solely to the female leader (sort of an Avatar⁸ setup), while in other cultures the chief was war leader, political boss, and head shaman. In a few, highly patriarchal cultures, both were male roles, and in a few, it simply depended on the most talented (spiritually) youth.

The role could oscillate, so to speak. What did not change were the presence of a chief, or of an advising shaman or astrologer, to guide that chief, and for good reason. It was the advisor's job to consider the gods, and their motions in the heavens above, to record them on the rocks and make recommendations. In the case of China, the shaman (wu⁹) would commune with the Above God, Shang Di, and divine the replies (cracks in tortoise shells and fossils¹⁰) to the plasmaglyphics. This role of advising the chief later became the role of the Jue Shi¹¹, or wandering persuaders/knights. Looking at the plasmaglyphics and plasmascripts of ancient China, we see plenty of motifs at play which support the origins of male and female roles.

The screenshot shows a website interface with a search bar at the top right containing the character '巫' and the text 'Etymology 搜索字源'. Below the search bar, there are four sections of search results:

- Oracle characters 甲骨文 (0)**: A message stating 'There is no known oracle characters found. 没有已知的甲骨文.'
- Bronze characters 金文 (1)**: A single character '巫' with a search ID 'B06891'.
- Seal characters 说文解字的篆字 (1)**: A single character '巫' in seal script with a search ID 'S03475'.
- Liushutong characters 六书通的字 (10)**: A grid of ten characters in various styles, including '巫' and '覡', with search IDs ranging from 'L03709' to 'L30924'.

⁸ "INT. BIO LAB - MORNING

JAKE pumps his chair across the lab, flanked by GRACE and NORM. Grace holds STEREO STILL PICTURES in front of him, one at a time -- images of clan members she has shot over the years -- a kind of flash card drill.

JAKE

Tsu'tey.(next photo)

Mo'at. (next photo)

Eytukan.

GRACE

He's the clan leader -- [indicating Eytukan]

(indicating Mo'at) -- but she's the spiritual leader. Like a shaman." <https://imsdb.com/scripts/Avatar.html>

⁹ Figure 2 - 巫 - "sorcerer" or "shaman" <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E5%B7%AB>

¹⁰ The use of mammoth bones probably related to the megafauna extinction event.

¹¹ 爵士 "wandering knight" (or persuaders); "sir"

ome 首页 About 汉字叔叔 Research 汉字研究

Etymology 搜索字源

Oracle characters 甲骨文 (18)

Q J12780	Q J12781	Q J12782	Q J12783	Q J12784	Q J12785	Q J12786
Q J12787	Q J12788	Q J12789	Q J12790	Q J12791	Q J12792	Q J12793
Q J12794	Q J12795	Q J12796	Q J12797			

Bronze characters 金文 (6)

Q B07891	Q B07892	Q B07893	Q B07894	Q B07895	Q B07896

Seal characters 说文解字的篆字 (1)

Q S03676

Figure 3 - Jue; credit: hanziyuan.net¹²

Here we see the great man, but in J12791 and J12793 we see signs of the pregnant god. And what does He-she give birth to? In S03676 we see the “cross”¹³ motif and the four bodies. We see also the authority of the thunderbolt in several glyphs, including an “awen” in J12797. The tripod is also obvious in the Bronze seals (Zhou dynasty). So we know that the tripod is the “triforce” motif in physical form. Notice it is a repeat of the themes, especially the two brothers/gas giant gods in Wu. We will circle back to this in the next section.

¹² <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E7%88%B5>

¹³ As noted in a previous paper, this Coelbren rune is, as in China, associated with destructive winds.
https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

Figure 4 - Jue Continued

In the Liushutong, however, we see far more dynamism. We see the tripod, yes, and the thunderbolt. We see clearly the two brother powers, the three sons, or triple-god (triune). We see the rays of the three sons that come down. In L37969 we see the unmistakable Saturn pictograph, and the all seeing eye motif within that. The thunderbolt or tri-force that unites is *above the planet-god* indicating the supremacy of the weapon or force. In many of these we see a bell or complete container, again indicating pregnancy. Perhaps the pregnant power is the Egg's power to create or destroy? Also, within the tripod we see clear identification in L27211 that a central authority is guiding the triune god's authority. So we see that in Taoism, the Lord is divided among three wise deities¹⁴. In Christianity, the three-faced God is Father, Son, and Ru'ach¹⁵.

In L37968-970 we see a repetition of S03676, which matches generally the religious beliefs out of the Golden Age (Megalithic Period to early Transition Period) about the balance of the Lagrange Arrangement¹⁶ of the gods. Each had their sphere of influence, and place in the above heavens.

Figure 5 - "Three Pure Ones" wisely governing Heaven; credit: Wikipedia

¹⁴ "Three Purities were the supreme Taoist deities: the Celestial Worthy of Primordial Beginning, the Celestial Worthy of Numinous Treasure, and the Celestial Worthy of the Tao and its Virtue. The rule over the highest three celestial realms of Jade Purity, Highest Purity, and Great Purity." <http://www.china.org.cn/english/daodejingforum/208124.htm>

¹⁵ Divine Wind, God's Breath, or Holy spirit

¹⁶

https://www.academia.edu/50939161/Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything pp. 44-45

Figure 6 - Shi; credit: Hanziyuan.net¹⁷

By contrast the etymology of Shi is rather straight forward. The cosmic pole with an above cross (Christian like) is in all the Shang, Zhou, and Han seals, and in L13596. However, the Liushutong seals also show our pregnant god, L13599, and even the repetition of a previous thunderbolt theme, the pulse looking glyph of L34128. But most importantly, we see what gives the Shi (sir knight) his advisory authority: the Great Man. L34131 and L34129 (which has the synchrotron toroid Dr. Peratt describes in his lab-based work), is clearly evident here.

The Great Man - Shang Di or Uchell (Coelbren/Khumry) - is the source of authority of the advisor.

Do we therefore blame the advisor for bad government, or the chief who is the war leader and political leader and head of the family? In the accounts of the Chinese visiting Cahokia we find a repetitive theme of the world: the Chinese deal strictly with the Chief Priest, as the Chief himself lives atop Monk's Mound¹⁸ to commune with the sun-god.¹⁹ This sun-god is now Apollo/Sol, and not Jupiter or Saturn or Shamash, but nevertheless that is where he resides. But the chief priest acts as a 'Shogun,' and guides the kingdom. In Japan the Emperor is also divine god on earth, and the Shogun²⁰ runs the kingdom.²¹ Again, this refers to Jupiter's (Enlil/Zeus) right to challenge the Brother/Father (Enki/Kronos), who becomes weak and even feminine!

Could therefore, the problem of government be that the evil overtakes the good?

How did this MIMS arise, and why does it produce problems? Was it meant originally to create the solution of: let's do what God wants!?

¹⁷ <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E5%A3%AB>

¹⁸ It may interest the reader to note that at Cahokia, two mounds which are conical and pyramidal, sit next to one another and are Saturn and Jupiter, respectively. These correspond to the Chinese zodiac known as "the divine marketplace." Of course, in ancient Greece, the agora was where their shi, the philosophers, would gather to win the favor of Senators. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/agora>

¹⁹ "To the Gates of Fengtu," L.B. Nickless, 2017

²⁰ Guess what motifs are found in the etymology for the word Shogun (將軍):

<https://hanziyuan.net/#%E5%B0%86> & <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E8%BB%8D>

²¹ In Chinese Medicine, the advisor becoming like the chief is seen as an usurpation of power and an act of evil. So if the Liver takes over the Heart, this is mutiny, and a sign of the decline of the royal family's ardour, and the general is usually not blamed, unless it is pure villainy.

In the next section we explore some of the Egyptian and Mesopotamian origins, in our quest to understand the MIMS of government, and the Divine Right to Rule²² motif²³.

Government in Antiquity

When asked how he would govern the People, Confucius replied that he would rectify the names and words²⁴. He also would have re-established the Rites and Poetry. He was a strong believer in centralized authority that came in Machiavellian style, from the Prince and State. The Prince was the State. But what kept it all working was the filial order of things.

Was this also a common belief in the Transition Period elsewhere? Study of Pharaonic Egypt in the Middle Kingdoms would seem to suggest it was. In fact, it was also important to the Egyptians which era of gods were in authority²⁵. As we know now, that Tutankamen's father, Akhenaten²⁶, tried to re-establish Ra (Shamash, the original dwarf star god), as Lord, and he married Tutankamen to his sister, Ankhesenpaaten. What's more strange is Akhenaten himself married his eldest daughter, Meritaten. This type of incest was an abomination even to the priests of Egypt. Why would he do this when it was known to them to create problems and even infertility?

Ankenaten had clearly been learning from the priests of the early gods, and reading of the relationship of the (what he didn't know were) planet-star gods. The creation of two brothers from a mother-father, and then the one brother making a third son, thereby becoming all of their fathers, and himself a son of himself. Then, to make matters stranger, the second but superior brother (as according to the Sumerians) then, as son (to the Babylonian and Greeks) defeats the elder brother, who was the divine ruler under the original. Remember, Anu (sky god) defeats his elder brother Alalu²⁷, to take the throne of the Annunaki.²⁸ So we know that this younger brother or son, defeating his elder brother or father, had precedent. But also, the elder or superior is then castrated²⁹, and becomes female!³⁰ The superior king, who nevertheless is a wandering philanderer³¹, marries his sister-queen³², and they bear the demigods (moons and rocky planets). Later, a he/she warrior god/dess (Venus) erupts from the elder brother/father/queen planet (Saturn) and goes on to mate with the smaller, but worshipful messiah son Horus/Heracles/Thor/Ares.³³ Then she fights him, scars him³⁴, and is enraged because he ends the reign of the superior Lord, planet Jupiter.³⁵ Innana/Medusa's rage turns upon the Earth and only the Lord (Horus/Christos) can save mankind. Nevertheless, planet Mars receives the credit.³⁶

²² <https://www.britannica.com/topic/divine-right-of-kings>

²³

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

²⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rectification_of_names

²⁵ This appears to be the habit of the Mayans as well, so much so that they even believed events of the past repeat in harmonics in the future. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M0vZAVCOAaI>

²⁶ <https://www.livescience.com/65433-king-tut-sisters-pharaoh.html>

²⁷ Is Alalu Hades/Uranus? <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Alalu>

²⁸ http://melammu-project.eu/database/gen_html/a0001230.html

²⁹ <https://digitalcommons.ciis.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1011&context=advance-archive>

³⁰ <https://mythology.stackexchange.com/questions/6114/examples-of-castration-myths-besides-ouranos>

³¹ https://www.greekmythology.com/Myths/The_Myths/Zeus's_Lovers/zeus's_lovers.html

³² <https://www.worldhistory.org/Hera>

³³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E3EVzBMBcRs>

³⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y

³⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Epic-of-Gilgamesh>

³⁶ Heracles defeats the monsters, while Thor wrestles the Midgard Serpent. Similar feats of the demi-god exist in Polynesian and aboriginal tales worldwide. <https://sites.pitt.edu/~dash/thorserpent.html>

This is a complicated story, full of intrigue, incest, war, and sexual congress. How else could Ankhenten regard it? He was, from all accounts, a bit of a madman. When he was killed, and his family ruined, the priests tried to erase his very existence from memory.³⁷ What was the source of their anger? Government policies from a megalomaniac, perversion of a tyrant, and endless or repetitious war campaigns?³⁸ Nothing drains the resources - the “purse” - of an empire or kingdom like war. We see from the “Art of War,” Sun Tzu has much to say on that subject.³⁹

But the question, to this author, is which is the primary reason, or is it truly the amalgamation of all of the above? A sort of Caesar/Caligula situation⁴⁰? The author tends to think so, and in particular we look at ancient attitudes about government, pre Middle Kingdom, and throughout the Megalithic Period⁴¹, which tend to suggest that the role of a leader was to establish peace, tranquility, agricultural fertility, and prevention of catastrophe, and to never be a tyrant.⁴²

In China this was manifested, legend says, through the tranquility of the Three Sovereigns⁴³, Yu, Yao⁴⁴, and Shun⁴⁵.

In short:

- ❖ Emperor Yu “the Great”: a rustic, almost barbarian king, he was said to have controlled the floods of the Deluge.⁴⁶
- ❖ Emperor Yao: a genius, able to fix the inundating flooding caused by the Deluge event “Like endless boiling water, the flood is pouring forth destruction. Boundless and overwhelming, it overtops hills and mountains. Rising and ever rising, it threatens the very heavens. How the people must be groaning and suffering!
— Emperor Yao, as quoted in the Book of History, describing the flood⁴⁷

Also, after the Jovian reign ended (causing the High Carp Flood⁴⁸), and the era of the New Sun began with Sol, no one had rectified the calendar when the planet flipped on its axis.⁴⁹ Legend has it that Yao did,

“According to some Chinese classic documents such as Yao Dian (Document of Yao) in Shang Shu (Book of Documents), and Wudibenji (Records for the Five Kings) in the Shiji (Historic Records), Yao assigned astronomic officers to observe celestial phenomena such as

³⁷ <http://www.usu.edu/markdamen/1320Hist&Civ/chapters/10AKHEN.htm>

³⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Akhenaten>

³⁹ “1. Sun Tzu said: In the operations of war, where there are in the field a thousand swift chariots, as many heavy chariots, and a hundred thousand mail-clad soldiers, with provisions enough to carry them a thousand li, the expenditure at home and at the front, including entertainment of guests, small items such as glue and paint, and sums spent on chariots and armor, will reach the total of a thousand ounces of silver per day. Such is the cost of raising an army of 100,000 men.”

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/jessicahagy/2013/10/03/sun-tzus-the-art-of-war-illustrated-chapter-2/?sh=29183684e600>

⁴⁰ <https://www.historyhit.com/worst-roman-emperors/>

⁴¹ 3500 BCE-600 BCE https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

⁴² <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3269343>

⁴³ https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/entry/Three_Sovereigns_and_Five_Emperors

⁴⁴

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320372005_The_Motif_of_Legendary_Emperors_Yao_and_Shun_in_Ancient_Chinese_Literature

⁴⁵ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24724948>

⁴⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yu_the_Great

⁴⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emperor_Yao

⁴⁸ https://www.academia.edu/51008599/Enki_and_The_World_Order

⁴⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formations_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

the sunrise, sunset, and the rising of the evening stars. This was done in order to make a solar and lunar calendar with 366 days for a year, also providing for the leap month.”

Legend has it he abdicated to his minister, Shun.

- ❖ Emperor Shun⁵⁰: minister of Yao, and again an enactor of several reforming policies which including reordering the lands, instituting worship of Shang Di⁵¹ (as state policy). He toured the country and rectified the governors and pacified the people. (war?) Note that he was a minister to Yao, and ended up in charge.⁵² He is revered for his ritual piety, and policies, and modesty.

The attitude of much of the world was this way. However, in Pharonic Egypt we see that as time goes on, the government becomes progenitors of slavery and expensive megalithic building⁵³, to the degree that it even threatens the state.^{54 55}

In Mexico, as well as Shang China⁵⁶, we see that government takes on increasingly the role of war kings, enslaving the enemy, and offering them up in sacrifice to the gods⁵⁷, particularly planet Venus.⁵⁸ Such a tradition continued in the Americas all the way until 1905 with the Pawnee⁵⁹. In Mexico it was stopped by the Spanish conquistador Cortez⁶⁰, but at Cahokia was still in place in at least 1433-1439.

So what was the purpose of government as a MIMS of that BC period? Clearly it was to bring about the betterment of lives (at first), which is the entire point of a MIMS. You/society/the king has ambitions for improvement, and then tries to bring about a potential reality. By communing directly with the “spirit world” and with the Lord⁶¹, this particular end is sought, and in some cases achieved.

The problem is that, after this, increasingly the pomp and power of the position of the king or divine ruler/shogun, what have you, is sought for its mimsical properties. Access, Influence, and Affluence⁶² are three properties of such a position which attract many kinds of men, of many varying belief systems. Some have greater intentions, like Ashoka the Great, or Alexander the Great, or even Kublai Khan⁶³. Others have petty intentions, or tyrannical intentions, and we know many more examples of the latter than the former.

In the end, the cosmology teaches us this was bound to happen. For after all, Zeus overthrowing Kronos was not an act of beneficence, but violence⁶⁴, and desire for position and tyranny. He dominated the skies, striking the gods⁶⁵, punishing and transfiguring demigods and mortals alike, and even potentially destroying Metis. What else could have formed the boluses of the Asteroid Belt⁶⁶? We do see specifically in the Enuma Elish that Marduk attacked the raging Tiamat, and killed her lover, Kingu,

⁵⁰ 2294 - 2184 BC; so First Kingdoms type era, definitely within the Megalithic Period, and no later than early Transition Period (if he existed).

⁵¹ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3269759>

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emperor_Shun

⁵³ https://www.ngu.no/upload/Publikasjoner/Special%20publication/SP12_s7-50.pdf

⁵⁴ https://www.worldhistory.org/Egyptian_Architecture/

⁵⁵ <https://www.nbcnews.com/id/wbna46485163>

⁵⁶ http://sino-platonic.org/complete/spp273_olmec_chinese_writing.pdf

⁵⁷ http://www.famsi.org/research/thesis_dissertations/KerkhoveR_thesis.pdf

⁵⁸ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/178547>

⁵⁹ <https://amertribes.proboards.com/thread/2570/dorsey-editor-pawnee-mythology-1906>

⁶⁰ <https://mospace.umsystem.edu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10355/11179/research.pdf?sequence=3>

⁶¹ https://www.academia.edu/33852373/Who_Answered_the_Shang_Diviner_The_Nature_of_Shang_Divination

⁶² “Axioms of Influence, Affluence, and Access,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2020

⁶³ <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Kublai-Khan>

⁶⁴ <http://myths.e2bn.org/mythsandlegends/userstory20415-zeus-vs-cronus.html>

⁶⁵ <https://www.thecollector.com/greek-mythology-rape-transformation/>

⁶⁶ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1993CeMDA..57...57N>

Enuma Elish

1. "But Marduk hath set out, the director of the gods, your son;
2. To set out against Tiamat his heart hath prompted him.
3. He opened his mouth and spake unto me, saying: "If I, your avenger,
4. Conquer Tiamat and give you life,
5. Appoint an assembly, make my fate preeminent and proclaim it.
6. In Upsukkinaku seat yourself joyfully together;
7. With my word in place of you will I decree fate.
8. May whatsoever I do remain unaltered,
9. May the word of my lips never be changed nor made of no avail."
10. Hasten, therefore, and swiftly decree for him the fate which you bestow,
11. That he may go and fight your strong enemy.
12. Gaga went, he took his way and
13. Humbly before Lahmu and Lahamu, the gods, his fathers,
14. He made obeisance, and he kissed the ground at their feet.
15. He humbled himself; then he stood up and spake unto them saying:
16. "Ansar, your son, hath sent me,
17. The purpose of his heart he hath made known unto me.
18. He saith that Tiamat our mother hath conceived a hatred for us,
19. With all her force she rageth, full of wrath.
20. All the gods have turned to her,
21. With those, whom ye created, they go at her side.
22. They are banded together and at the side of Tiamat they advance;
23. They are furious, they devise mischief without resting night and day.
24. They prepare for battle, fuming and raging;
25. They have joined their forces and are making war.
26. Ummu-Hubur, who formed all things,
27. Hath made in addition weapons invincible; she hath spawned monster-serpents,
28. Sharp of tooth and merciless of fang.
29. With poison, instead of blood, she hath filled their bodies.
30. Fierce monster-vipers she hath clothed with terror,
31. With splendor she hath decked them, she hath made them of lofty stature.
32. Whoever beboldeth them, terror overcometh him,
33. Their bodies rear up and none can withstand their attack.
34. She hath set up vipers, and dragons, and the monster Lahamu,
35. And hurricanes, and raging hounds, and scorpion-men,
36. And mighty tempests, and fish-men, and rams;
37. They bear merciless weapons, without fear of the fight.
38. Her commands are mighty; none can resist them;
39. After this fashion, huge of stature, hath she made eleven monsters.
40. Among the gods who are her sons, inasmuch as he hath given her support,
41. She hath exalted Kingu; in their midst she hath raised him to power.
42. To march before the forces, to lead the host,
43. To give the battle-signal, to advance to the attack, To direct the battle, to control the fight,
44. Unto him hath she entrusted; in costly raiment she hath made him sit, saying:

45. I have uttered thy spell; in the assembly of the gods I have raised thee to power,
 46. The dominion over all the gods have I entrusted unto thee.
 47. Be thou exalted, thou my chosen spouse,
 48. May they magnify thy name over all of them...the Anunnaki.
 49. She hath given him the Tablets of Destiny on his breast she laid them, saying:
 50. Thy command shall not be without avail, and the word of thy mouth shall be established.'
 51. Now Kingu, thus exalted, **having received the power of Anu,**
 52. Decreed the fate for the gods, her sons, saying:
 53. 'Let the opening of your mouth quench the Fire-god;
 54. Whoso is exalted in the battle, let him display his might!'
 55. I sent Anu, but he could not withstand her;
 56. Nudimmud was afraid and turned back.
 57. But Marduk hath set out, the director of the gods, your son;
 58. To set out against Tiamat his heart hath prompted him.
 59. He opened his mouth and spake unto me, saying:
 60. 'If I, your avenger,
 61. Conquer Tiamat and give you life,
 62. Appoint an assembly, make my fate preeminent and proclaim it.
 63. In Upsukkinaku seat yourselves joyfully together;
 64. With my word in place of you will I decree fate.
 65. May, whatsoever I do remain unaltered,
 66. May the word of my lips never be changed nor made of no avail.'
 67. Hasten, therefore, and swiftly decree for him the fate which you bestow,
 68. That he may go and fight your strong enemy!
 69. Lahmu and Lahamu heard and cried aloud
 70. All of the Igigi [The elder gods] wailed bitterly, saying:
 71. What has been altered so that they should
 72. We do not understand the deed of Tiamat!
 73. Then did they collect and go,
 74. The great gods, all of them, who decree fate.
 75. ...
 76. Then for Marduk, their avenger, did they decree the fate.
 ...
 77. "O Marduk, thou art our avenger!
 78. We give thee sovereignty over the whole world.
 79. Sit thou down in might; be exalted in thy command.
 80. Thy weapon shall never lose its power; it shall crush thy foe.
 81. O Lord, spare the life of him that putteth his trust in thee,
 82. But as for the god who began the rebellion, pour out his life."
 83. Then set they in their midst a garment,
 84. And unto Marduk,- their first-born they spake:
 85. "May thy fate, O lord, be supreme among the gods,
 86. To destroy and to create; speak thou the word, and thy command shall be fulfilled.
 87. Command now and let the garment vanish;
 88. And speak the word again and let the garment reappear!

89. Then he spake with his mouth, and the garment vanished;
 90. Again he commanded it, and. the garment reappeared.
 91. When the gods, his fathers, beheld the fulfillment of his word,
 92. They rejoiced, and they did homage unto him, saying, " Marduk is king!"
 93. They bestowed upon him the scepter, and the throne, and the ring,
 94. They give him an invincible weaponry which overwhelmeth the foe.
 95. Go, and cut off the life of Tiamat,
 96. And let the wind carry her blood into secret places."
 97. After the gods his fathers had decreed for the lord his fate,
 98. They caused him to set out on a path of prosperity and success.
 99. He made ready the bow, he chose his weapon,
 100. He slung a spear upon him and fastened it...
 101. He raised the club, in his right hand he grasped it,
 102. The bow and the quiver he hung at his side.
 103. He set the lightning in front of him,
 104. With burning flame he filled his body.
 105. He made a net to enclose the inward parts of Tiamat,
 106. The four winds he stationed so that nothing of her might escape;
 107. The South wind and the North wind and the East wind and the West wind
 108. He brought near to the net, the gift of his father Anu.
 109. He created the evil wind, and the tempest, and the hurricane,
 110. And the fourfold wind, and the sevenfold wind, and the whirlwind, and the wind which
 had no equal;
 111. He sent forth the winds which he had created, the seven of them;
 112. To disturb the inward parts of Tiamat, they followed after him.
 113. Then the lord raised the thunderbolt, his mighty weapon,
 114. He mounted the chariot, the storm unequaled for terror,
 115. He harnessed and yoked unto it four horses,
 116. Destructive, ferocious, overwhelming, and swift of pace;
 117. ... were their teeth, they were flecked with foam;
 118. They were skilled in... , they had been trained to trample underfoot.
 119. mighty in battle,
 120. Left and right...
 121. His garment was... , he was clothed with terror,
 122. With overpowering brightness his head was crowned.⁶⁷
 123. Then he set out, he took his way,
 124. And toward the raging Tiamat he set his face.
 125. On his lips he held ...,
 126. ... he grasped in his hand.
 127. Then they beheld him, the gods beheld him,
 128. The gods his fathers beheld him, the gods beheld him.
 129. And the Lord drew nigh, he gazed upon the inward parts of Tiamat,
 130. He perceived the muttering of Kingu, her spouse.

⁶⁷ The aurora of Jupiter comes from the high energy Birkeland Currents:
<https://www.inverse.com/science/juno-jupiter-aurora-discovery>

131. As Marduk gazed, Kingu was troubled in his gait,
 132. His will was destroyed and his motions ceased.
 133. And the gods, his helpers, who marched by his side,
 134. Beheld their leader's..., and their sight was troubled.
 135. But Tiamat... , she turned not her neck,
 136. With lips that failed not she uttered rebellious words:
 137. "... thy coming as lord of the gods,
 138. From their places have they gathered, in thy place are they! "
 139. Then the lord raised the thunderbolt, his mighty weapon,
 140. And against Tiamat, who was raging, thus he sent the word:
 141. Thou art become great, thou hast exalted thyself on high,
 142. And thy heart hath prompted thee to call to battle.
 143. ... their fathers...,
 144. ... their... thou hatest...
 145. Thou hast exalted Kingu to be thy spouse,
 146. Thou hast... him, that, even as Anu, he should issue decrees.
 147. thou hast followed after evil,
 148. And against the gods my fathers thou hast contrived thy wicked plan.
 149. Let then thy host be equipped, let thy weapons be girded on!
 150. Stand! I and thou, let us join battle!
 151. When Tiamat heard these words,
 152. She was like one possessed, she lost her reason.
 153. Tiamat uttered wild, piercing cries,
 154. She trembled and shook to her very foundations.
 155. She recited an incantation, she pronounced her spell,
 156. And the gods of the battle cried out for their weapons.
 157. Then advanced Tiamat and Marduk, the counselor of the gods;
 158. To the fight they came on, to the battle they drew nigh.
 159. The lord spread out his net and caught her,
 160. And the evil wind that was behind him he let loose in her face.
 161. As Tiamat opened her mouth to its full extent,
 162. He drove in the evil wind⁶⁸, while as yet she had not shut her lips.
 163. The terrible winds filled her belly,
 164. And her courage was taken from her, and her mouth she opened wide.
 165. He seized the spear and burst her belly,
 166. He severed her inward parts, he pierced her heart.
 167. He overcame her and cut off her life;
 168. He cast down her body and stood upon it.
 169. When he had slain Tiamat, the leader,
 170. Her might was broken, her host was scattered.
 171. And the gods her helpers, who marched by her side,
 172. Trembled, and were afraid, and turned back.
 173. They took to flight to save their lives;
 174. But they were surrounded, so that they could not escape.

⁶⁸ The "croess" motif in Coelbren, aka the swastika. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swastika>

175. He took them captive, he broke their weapons;
 176. In the net they were caught and in the snare they sat down.
 177. The ... of the world they filled with cries of grief.
 178. They received punishment from him, they were held in bondage.
 179. And on the eleven creatures which she had filled with the power of striking terror,
 180. Upon the troop of devils, who marched at her...,
 181. He brought affliction, their strength he...;
 182. Them and their opposition he trampled under his feet.
 183. Moreover, Kingu, who had been exalted over them,
 184. He conquered, and with the god Dug-ga he counted him.
185. He took from him the Tablets of Destiny that were not rightly his,
 186. He sealed them with a seal and in his own breast he laid them.
 187. Now after the hero Marduk had conquered and cast down his enemies,
 188. And had made the arrogant foe even like
 189. And had fully established Ansar's triumph over the enemy
 190. And had attained the purpose of Nudimmud,
 191. Over the captive gods he strengthened his durance,
192. And unto Tiamat, whom he had conquered, he returned.
193. And the lord stood upon Tiamat's hinder parts,
194. And with his merciless club he smashed her skull.
195. He cut through the channels of her blood,
 196. And he made the North wind bear it away into secret places.
 197. His fathers beheld, and they rejoiced and were glad;
 198. Presents and gifts they brought unto him.
 199. Then the lord rested, gazing upon her dead body,
 200. While he divided the flesh of the ... , and devised a cunning plan.
 201. He split her up like a flat fish into two halves;
 202. One half of her he established as a covering for heaven.
 203. He fixed a bolt, he stationed a watchman,
 204. And bade them not to let her waters come forth.
 205. He passed through the heavens, he surveyed the regions thereof,
 206. And over against the Deep he set the dwelling of Nudimmud.
 207. And the lord measured the structure of the Deep,
 208. And he founded E-sara, a mansion like unto it.
 209. The mansion E-sara which he created as heaven,
 210. He caused Anu, Bel, and Ea in their districts to inhabit."⁶⁹

Anu is likely planet Saturn, Bel is likely planet Uranus, and Ea as a blue sky-god, is almost certainly planet Neptune, in these contexts. The difficulty is that the Sumero-Babylonians had multiple names for these same bodies^{70 71}, depending on which state they were in (glow/arc mode or dark mode/normal).

⁶⁹ Tablets 3 & 4, selections, with emphasis added; <https://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm>

⁷⁰ <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/221/the-mesopotamian-pantheon/>

⁷¹ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/9781444308549.app1>

Seeing the description of the Clash of the Titans⁷² from those who recently witnessed it, much can be said. But what needs to be said is how obviously intertwined with war early governance - or the perception of governance, ie the "Tablets of Destiny" - was, almost from the outset. For if not for Marduk, then the winds of destruction of Tiamat, and the weapons of the gods of Enki and the Tablets of Destiny themselves would all still exist in our modern world. In other words, we should expect that already at that time (as we shall see all the way back to 7kya), the habits of war were part of the formative ideas of government.

Failed Ancient Government Programs

What type of government programs have we seen in pre-modern history, which boggle the mind, and present a difficulty for describing government as a good MIMS (post Flood)? What horrors awaited mankind, hidden beneath the guise of "collective good," or "benevolence⁷³," or "Heaven's Will?"; the latter the author discussed in length in terms of fortune and Aether (A power), in a previous paper⁷⁴. Presuming the good will of the government, would be to presume the continuous application of those in power to the seeking of proper, healthy solutions that benefit all, and create good fortunes for the city, county, country or state. As we have seen definitely with COVID and some governors' behaviors⁷⁵, this is clearly not so.⁷⁶ But we digress.

Now in ancient Mexico, as has been described, the Olmec instituted a government policy of human sacrifice. We have plenty of pits to prove this. The large, spherical Olmec heads (gods), make it clear that their Megalithic Period religion was dedicated to the gods, and the prescribed behavior (or so they divined, probably because a shaman using auto-dictation told them so), was clearly bent towards rectifying the barbarians (by sacrificing them). The same basic belief was in Cahokia, as has been said.⁷⁷ Why would this need to be done?

It has to do with either the death of the star, and what happened as it exploded and birthed material out (burning some things and birthing others). Or it has to do with the arc mode of planets Neptune and Jupiter as they sought to equalize charge distribution in the "Tree of Life" (Yggdrasil), whenever the three body solution (pre Lagrange when charge had been equalized) brought things in too close to one another.

What is interesting to understand is that there is some evidence for government programs to describe the star event in the Tepe Period at Gobekli Tepe. There is also the brief speculation of the Egyptian Priest to Solon that the Atlanteans brought destruction upon themselves.⁷⁸ But though we wish for there to be early electric power sources pre Giza, and there must be development prior to the engineering of that masterpiece, we cannot prove his statements, which are third hand.

However, the natives of the world do agree with Babylonian⁷⁹ and Biblical accounts that Jupiter caused the flood in order to punish mankind. The Navajo specifically reference that the Creator (Lord) wished to

⁷² <https://www.worldhistory.org/Titan/>

⁷³ "late Middle English: from Old French benivolent, from Latin bene volent- 'well wishing', from bene 'well' + velle 'to wish'" (Oxford Languages). Isn't it curious how similar that word is to "violence"? "Middle English: via Old French from Latin violentia, from violent- 'vehement, violent'" Curious.

⁷⁴

https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether

⁷⁵ Cuomo, Whitmer, and Newsome particularly.

⁷⁶

<https://patriotalerts.com/2021/08/nys-new-gov-announces-that-cuomos-nursing-home-scandal-was-way-worse-than-earlier-reported/>

⁷⁷ Specifically the scourging of flesh to eliminate sin, as we see in certain cultures, in the cults of Catholicism, and as the Hebrew did to Yeshua.

⁷⁸ <http://www.strangehistory.net/2014/02/22/plato-meets-the-meteorite-solon-egypt-and-atlantis/>

⁷⁹ See: The Atrahasis Text <https://geha.paginas.ufsc.br/files/2017/04/Atrahasis.pdf>

destroy the “Evil Animals and People,” while the Delaware told Thomas Jefferson that the Great Man killed the “tremendous animals” at Big Bone Lick, KY, in order to punish them for destroying the bear, deer, and elk meant for mankind.⁸⁰ Presumably this was a way to explain the selectiveness of step potential upon the megafauna.⁸¹ It’s clearly non-scientific, and incorrect, but nevertheless the government of the tribe - the Chief - had had this story handed down to him since the Jovian era.

What are we to make of this application of the Thunderbolts and arcs of electricity, and of the various weapons of the gods (bolides, divine winds, tsunamis, floods, and volcanos)?

Let us look, briefly, at the chief event of interest to the Middle East of the Megalithic Period: the interaction of Mars and Venus in close conjunction. First, the event has been described as “lovers mating”, “a child at the breast,” and a battle of two war gods.⁸² In the end the “bull” (or cow) wins... but in the legends, the Heracleian hero - Gilgamesh or Houyi or Mars - kills the Bull of Heaven in the age of Taurus (Jovian era), ending Jupiter’s reign!

Slide 1 - Athena Imagery;
credit: P. Pickles⁸³

As it turns out this is a different set of horns, and refers to the comet tail⁸⁴ of the Great comet (or Death Star) Venus!⁸⁵ But what’s important is how these horns became replicated. In some cases, yes there was a golden calf or idol. But in most of the world the comet was replicated in *war helms*. And what did Venus do to the messianic (and red) war god? She scoured his Northern Hemisphere, leaving tracts of desolation, and a great scar upon his cheek⁸⁶. This sent the war god into a berserker rage that inspired 400

⁸⁰ https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

⁸¹ Ibid. see Part 4

⁸² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7R0pu6SReto>

⁸³ <https://slideplayer.com/slide/4110893/> Note that the Medusa is the alter ego of planet Venus, and the Owl motif refers to the Mars and Venus opposition, but is an older motif back to when Jupiter and proto-Saturn (mother of Kronos) first separated, creating the male-female motif that Mars and Venus repeated. Remember that Shamash dies and births himself (mother of himself as Saturn), and becomes his own son and brother to the Superior Jupiter, before being castrated to become Hera/sister/Queen. Venus emerges from Saturn, but later passes through Jupiter’s atmosphere, and becomes inflamed and a warrior-princess of Zeus. Hera is “jealous” and sends Heracles (Mars) as her champion.

⁸⁴ <https://www.mpg.de/6885096/venus-tail>

⁸⁵ <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1987sici.symp...38P/abstract>

⁸⁶ Valles Marineris; Venus cont’d: Note that the war helm in the statue is pointed, but cultural DNA reveals many; remember the shell motif, the red plume. Indeed the plume is the symbol of Saturn’s sickle. However, the red dust gives hint to the proper war god of that motif, the archetypal hero: Hercules/Houyi/Ares. Sometimes the battles of Thor and Loki were matters of strength, but many times matters of trickery, and death. It is easy to confuse the plume with the shell motif, which goes back as far as 5.5kya. However, remember also that comets are associated with plagues. Proud plumes are almost assuredly associated with the masculine Mars.Red dust most definitely is. So we should expect those red Roman plumes to be only since the Transition Period.

Recognizing Athena in Imagery

- Portrayed wearing a full suit of armor with helmet raised in order for her face to be visible
- Carries a spear and shield with the gorgoneion (the head of the gorgon Medusa) at the center, her aegis also has this symbol on it
- Often depicted with an owl on her shoulder

c. 450 B.C.

years of dark ages of war in Greece and in China, and inspired the fighting martial tradition of Sumo⁸⁷, among others.

But Venus scourged Mars. It was visible. His face was scarred.⁸⁸

So governments also took to scourging. As we return to Mexico, bear this in mind as we look at the arrival of Cortez in 1519. When Cortez arrived, he was aided (this is in brief) by the native rivals of the Mexica (Aztecs)⁸⁹. The Mexica at first invited the Viracocha-like conquistador in, thinking him a new Quetzlcoatl⁹⁰, but then later drove the Spanish out because of their “blaspheme” against the gods, through vigorous protests against the Satanic practice of ritual heart sacrifice⁹¹. In particular there was one festival in which over 100,000 slaves, virgins (boys?⁹²), and warriors had their hearts ripped out upon the Jovian inspired pyramid in Tenochtitlan. It was a horrific sight. The Spanish had the technology, but had to flee through the lake.

They came back for vengeance⁹³, though, with their native allies (seeking revenge for the heart sacrifices and excesses of the Mexica), and they conquered easily.

Thus ended one bad government program, which was likely prescribed as a result of the continual need to fight cowpox (so they would have thought) which had arrived in the 1430s from the Chinese in Cahokia⁹⁴ and likely spread through typical trade up and down the rivers and coasts. Was it a program to eradicate cowpox and VD via heart sacrifice? As it happens, and may interest the reader, the Chinese solution to the mess they caused/spread when they made war in the “Four Rivers” region (probably against the Padoucans/Ft. Ancient/Welsh Indians): paint magical dragons upon the cliff and then *just leave*.⁹⁵ Later the fleet was burned when the 1491 comet went by and caused a massive tsunami and the emperor of China interpreted it as punishment for the Zheng He voyage’s catastrophe in America! The remains were burned and can still be seen on the shores.⁹⁶

So the Spanish stop one bad government program, and then reign in peace, right? Wrong. They knock over the temple, build a church, burn the Aztec/Maya⁹⁷ codices, enslave the population, and then spread smallpox, decimating the Mexica and the natives of Central and North America. Through arrogance, they rob the empires of the Aztecs and Inca, and bring wanton death and destruction, and then later have so much gold they crash the world economy!⁹⁸

⁸⁷ https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God

⁸⁸ Here the work of the inestimable Ev Cochrane (“Starf*cker”), and of Dave Talbott (“The Saturn Myth”) is really indispensable. A complete review of the “Discourses of an Alien Sky,” without becoming tied to the Polar Configuration is recommended: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ALfHeZQVEoI&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UeFB-ygaH63Seq6r6C_dtqB

⁸⁹

<https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/americas/montezuma-s-revenge-cannibalism-in-the-age-of-the-conquistadors-413272.html>

⁹⁰ Plumed Serpent: Midgard Serpent? Venus? This might be so, but probably only as a double replication of the Saturn motif, for we are certain that originally he was Saturn, and his heart exploded out to become the Evening/Morning Star.

<http://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

⁹¹ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Battle-of-Tenochtitlan>

⁹²

<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-mexico-sacrifice/ancient-maya-sacrificed-boys-not-virgin-girls-study-idUSWRI32680820080123>

⁹³ <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2015/oct/10/conquistadors-sacrificed-eaten-aztec-acolhuas>

⁹⁴ “To the Gates of Fengtu,” L.B Nickless, 2015

⁹⁵ “Chasing Dragons: the True History of the Piasa,” M. Nickless, 2012

⁹⁶ <https://www.businessinsider.com/china-zheng-he-treasure-fleet-elite-free-trade-2017-2>

⁹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M0vZAVCOAaI>

⁹⁸

<https://history.stackexchange.com/questions/9060/how-did-the-gold-of-the-new-world-cause-the-spanish-empire-to-collapse>

So much for the genius of government programs in the New World and Orient. How did this affect the Age of Exploration and the later Renaissance? It was because of the collapse of the Spanish Empire that the British Empire⁹⁹ was able to start¹⁰⁰. It was Queen Elizabeth who took an unspeakable economic risk and backed the Dutch East India company, and this fueled economic growth¹⁰¹. By this growth, the Americas were conquered, and the world colonized. Not all of it bad, but most can agree, the policies, particularly the enslavement of those on Easter Island¹⁰² and the behavior of Cook's men at Hawaii¹⁰³, and the apartheid in Africa to govern it (by all European nations) were particularly atrocious.

Why was this, and of course the African "Triangle Trade"¹⁰⁴ acceptable to the governments? Religion said that non-whites were not human.¹⁰⁵ Why would they say that? Pure bias? No, it was again the excuse of the Divine Right to Rule - the same reasoning given by the tyrant Louis VI for the exorbitant decorations at Versailles which bankrupted France - to essentially scourge the peasantry, or colonies, for all their worth¹⁰⁶. As is seen throughout human history, the prerogative of the government (and of tyrants) is to act as if it is natural for everything to flow towards them. The Chinese put it this way, the grass bends before the wind (blowing from the Prince).¹⁰⁷ Why put it this way? Because as was seen in the Enuma Elish, the winds of destruction flew before Tiamat, and then when she was killed, they flew before Marduk! It is, from the end of the cataclysms to now, a long story of a quest for mankind to become godlike in power over one another through government programs. It is what motivates China/PLA to this very day! Can there be any doubt that the reason China so strongly researches plasma fusion¹⁰⁸, and collects the world's largest copper boulder¹⁰⁹, and promotes the cataclysmic histories, and space domination¹¹⁰... all related to a quest to have the world's first Perattian Thunderbolt Generator?¹¹¹ The Soviets and Americans stopped certain types of nuclear testing¹¹², once electrical behaviors that could be as devastating to mankind and developed (electrified) nations were discovered¹¹³... but the Chinese have no such agreement, and are very active in space.^{114 115 116}

Government programs - from Shang and Olmec human sacrifice, to Egyptian and Qinshihuangdi's megalithic building through slavery¹¹⁷, to Aztec and Spanish and Chinese bungling in the Americas of how to deal with the pox, to the British (and others') Empire's racist colonization, all have in common a belief in natural

⁹⁹ <https://www.britannica.com/summary/British-Empire-Timeline>

¹⁰⁰ [https://dailyhistory.org/How_did_the_defeat_of_the_Spanish_Armada_\(1588\)_change_England%3F](https://dailyhistory.org/How_did_the_defeat_of_the_Spanish_Armada_(1588)_change_England%3F)

¹⁰¹ "GRUNCH of Giants," B. Fuller, 1983

¹⁰² <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/10/12/science/easter-island-dna-south-america.html>

¹⁰³ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25169289>

¹⁰⁴ As we remember that even Native Americans and Black freedmen owned black slaves, it was the African tribal governments, and Islamic slavers who sold them to the European powers. All around, an atrocious capital market. Here in Lexington there are still two streets: Cheapside and Quality. What does the reader imagine this means? Shameful, but true history.

¹⁰⁵ <http://nationalhumanitiescenter.org/pds/becomingamer/peoples/text3/indianscolonists.pdf>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.livescience.com/38903-palace-of-versailles-facts-history.html>

¹⁰⁷ "The green reed which bends in the wind is stronger than the mighty oak which breaks in a storm." ~Confucius
https://www.chinesethought.cn/EN/shuyu_show.aspx?shuyu_id=4131

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.popularmechanics.com/science/energy/a36630528/china-artificial-sun-breaks-fusion-world-record/>

¹⁰⁹ However, an American did buy *back* from China the largest chunk of float copper!
<https://collectorsedge.com/news-updates/collectors-edge-minerals-purchases-the-worlds-largest-float-copper/>

¹¹⁰ <https://fortune.com/2021/05/30/china-space-race-rocket-landing-mars-us/>

¹¹¹ <https://www.nationaldefensemagazine.org/articles/2021/4/8/study-sheds-light-on-chinese-directed-energy-program>

¹¹² <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/soviets-ratify-treaty-banning-nuclear-weapons-from-outer-space>

¹¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KcTrOGS3TyE>

¹¹⁴ <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2005-12/features/actionreaction-us-space-weaponization-china>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.amacad.org/publication/russian-and-chinese-responses-us-military-plans-space/section/4>

¹¹⁶ https://cgsr.llnl.gov/content/assets/docs/Gottemoeller_TWQ_43-3.pdf

¹¹⁷ <https://books.google.com/books?id=YbKLDwAAQBAJ>

authority of the governing to scourge the governed. This is not an accident, or a simple case of bully psychology. It is the enabling of mankind, the ascent to the power of authorities, which has been called human self-domestication¹¹⁸. It means that the poor (and religious) do, and maybe always will, “render unto Caesar what is Caesar’s.” Because Caesar, just as the Bohemian Grove¹¹⁹ nutjobs¹²⁰ of today, and the pedophile elite like Jeffrey Epstein, Prince Andrew, and Jimmy Savile, etc., had crazy government programs (like shooting nine of ten bulls dead because Mars/Houyi “shot 9 out of 10 suns”¹²¹). The whimsical beliefs of the nobility are renowned, because the horror of their excessive, grotesque, brutal, and inexcusable (and yet unpunished) behaviors are traceable, understandable, and maybe even predictable, due to cosmological origins.

From this, then, we may also see that it is almost with a terror-gestalt that we observe the train-like momentum of the NWO and Deep State elite to push mankind towards world-ending scenarios by building, researching, stockpiling the weapons of the gods... with no plans to use them responsibly¹²² (like destroying asteroids¹²³), and we also can examine the almost opiate belief of the masses that the gods will save them from these megalomaniacs. What is terrifying is that the peasantry does not understand, and has never understood, that it was the gods that “gave permission” to the nobility to do these things. With money and economics and government being what it is today, the nobility no longer even worry (as they did in the days of Sumer) whether or not they wreck the planet or kill millions. They don’t ask for permission. They just do it.

Mankind’s Quest for the Weapons of the Gods

In a previous paper, the author revealed the shocking amount of money spent by the US Government since 1941 on nuclear weapons. In this paper those values will be updated, as well as reasonable estimates on costs of other major powers programs. Estimates measuring the value of food will be given. However, before doing that, the author wishes to briefly recount a) the ancient origins of weaponry and b) the kinds of destructive “weapons” of the gods which exist in mythic accounts. It does appear that mankind is seeking to develop these (or pitifully small versions of them), instead of a) feeding the children and homeless of the world, b) seriously developing means of surviving space, c) or catastrophes, and d) curing serious diseases.¹²⁴

The original weapons that mankind had are all inspired by the thunderbolts and bolides: slings, atl-atls, spears, arrows, swords, and halberds are all found in symbols in plasmaglyphs, and pictographs throughout the world. Moreover, the halberd or specifically trident, is found in many basic forms as a weapon¹²⁵ wielding by the Sea/Sky God, and is the older motif. The sword, spear, and arrow are all associated with Jupiter/Marduk. Odin’s sword¹²⁶, for example, is said to be sheathed but once unsheathed will start Ragnarok.¹²⁷ The Arrow of Brahma was said to be able to vaporize entire cities! When we see the size of the Richat Formation, Upheaval

¹¹⁸ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/02/180215110041.htm>

¹¹⁹ “The Bohemian Grove: Facts & Fiction,” M. Dice, 2015

¹²⁰ “One example was President Richard Nixon’s comments from a May 13, 1971, tape recording talking about upper-class San Franciscans: “The Bohemian Grove, which I attend from time to time—it is the most faggy goddamned thing you could ever imagine, with that San Francisco crowd.” (sic) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bohemian_Grove And this is from Tricky Dick, who attended! Doesn’t speak well for the type of crowd.

¹²¹ <https://mythopedia.com/chinese-mythology/gods/hou-yi/>

¹²² <https://www.popularmechanics.com/space/a36122690/government-tests-using-nuclear-weapons-to-deflect-asteroids/>

¹²³ The idea that you make more dangerous asteroids is a bit hilarious. The point is they are then smaller. Size is directly related to extinction. Perhaps the government is just trolling with this “model” stuff? Because it is clearly better to make smaller bolides.

¹²⁴ Sadly, we cannot talk about these major needs because politics and war has become so toxic, and Big Tech so one-party censorial and detached from reality, that we cannot even have reasonable discussions.

¹²⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trishula>

¹²⁶ <https://blog.vkngjewelry.com/en/weapons-norse-mythology/>

¹²⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ragnar%C3%B6k>

Dome¹²⁸, Ayers Rock, Stone Mountain, the Knobs Region, and other electro-geological formations¹²⁹, this is not too hard an idea to understand. The power even of a single stroke Perattian Thunderbolt is hydrogen bomb range at minimum¹³⁰. How much more so can the bolts that carved the Valles Marineris or raise Olympus Mons¹³¹? Continuous discharge would absolutely destroy large civilizations, and buckling the crust of the Earth and causing collapse of entire land masses would be simple for the PEMF. Its power is way beyond human comprehension as it is 10³⁸ to 10⁴⁰ times stronger than gravity!

Of the ways that these thunderbolts affect the Earth, compare with the various weapons of the gods, covered in our previous paper.

Table 1 - Weapons of the Gods

Effects of Arc Blast ^{132 133}	Weapon of the gods	Mythic Citations
High heat/vitrification	Thunderbolt / Vajra ¹³⁴	Welsh Arthurian Legends ¹³⁵
Winds of Destruction	Huracan ¹³⁶ /Tai Feng	Hindu, Mayan & Chinese sources
Flooding/Tsunamis	High Carp Floods & Deluge	Enki & World Order ¹³⁷ , Atrahasis
Discharge Machining/Terraforming	Cosmic Hammer	Raising of Devil's Tower ¹³⁸
Step Potential	Cosmic Scythe ¹³⁹	Lot's Wife/Pillar of Dust ¹⁴⁰

When we look at the mythic recounting, and then compare with the remnants of sites, Dwarka, Sodom (what we think¹⁴¹), the vitrification at forts and temples, the instant petrification on the shores of Australia¹⁴², the crypto explosive nuclear-like nanospherules in Mesopotamia, and the repeated stories of mass death associated with comets, cosmic events, the mammoths whose feet remain planted as their bodies are blasted

¹²⁸

https://becomingborealis.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Electric-Discharge-Caused-the-Formation-of-Upheaval-Dome_002.pdf

¹²⁹ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

¹³⁰ The cosmic Thunderbolts were the inspiration of the spear, trident, sword, and arrow. The "Arrow of Brahma" was said to vaporize whole cities, probably in reference to Harappa. However, the author's own calculations confirm the power level to be roughly 10-1,000x the Bikini H-bomb, at minimum (single stroke). The blasts of a single ray of the 56 rays is estimated to be hundreds of thousands to millions of amps.

<https://plasmauniverse.info/downloads-petros/Peratt&YaoAurora-PrehistoryPhys-Scr-T131.2008c.pdf>

¹³¹ Which is definitely not a shield volcano. See previously cited "Symbols of an Alien Sky, part 2"

¹³² Synchronistically released video from Andy Hall: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pt6NscQ2qS8>

¹³³ More Andy Hall <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>

¹³⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vajra>

¹³⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vitrified_fort

¹³⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Huracan>

¹³⁷ https://www.academia.edu/51008599/Enki_and_The_World_Order

¹³⁸ <https://indiancountrytoday.com/archive/the-legend-of-devils-tower>

¹³⁹ <https://www.britannica.com/story/where-does-the-concept-of-a-grim-reaper-come-from>

¹⁴⁰ Salt is a mistranslation of the Hebrew for dust. They are alternates.

¹⁴¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dlusq1FXHNQ>

¹⁴² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5vOMGQTjW9k>

away¹⁴³, etc. it is a little difficult to believe that the anthropological and greater archaeological community cannot summon the imagination for planet-wide catastrophe¹⁴⁴. Nevertheless, between the isotopes of Saturn's rings matching Earth's water¹⁴⁵, and the electrogeological sites, and the overall mass of cross comparative mythology, linguistics, and plasma lab experimentation¹⁴⁶, they really have no choice but to evolve and then spend the next 200 years of youthful regeneration revisiting the native myths, and ancient cultures' testimony. As they do so, many old assumptions will be completely overturned; it has already begun. The data will only continue to mount. This will rise as a tidal wave or tsunami, and crest overtop the gatekeepers. AI may also lead the way.

But there can be no doubt that mankind was inspired. Now the question for us is to *what degree* has this inspired our cultural DNA/memory, worldwide, and to what lengths has mankind gone to try to utilize this knowledge, even cathartically¹⁴⁷?

As we shall see, quite far, although it isn't known how far since many inspirations (modern or ancient) are active attempts. For example, are electrical arc laser-plasma experiments¹⁴⁸, or plasma fusion experiments related to the desire to make a defacto "Ion Cannon" (thunderbolt generator)? This we cannot know without declassification, and this type of work probably would not be declassified (especially during a New Cold War) for 40 or more years.

Figure 7 - Ion Cannon (Perattian Thunderbolt) in Skyrim ([gif](#))¹⁴⁹

Data and citations¹⁵⁰ found here: <https://bit.ly/3msrMHs>

¹⁴³ See the Megafauna Extinction paper for details like these, and also on lightning step potential cases that have happened in modern/recent history.

https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

¹⁴⁴ Or nearly as bad, the altstream can only imagine comets or the like, and fail to understand scope and energy scales. See Part 2 of the above paper.

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.psi.edu/news/phoebewater>

¹⁴⁶ Dr. Peratt, Bill Yelverton, Andy Hall, etc.

¹⁴⁷ Think: blowing up the Death Star in Star Wars... and Return of the Jedi, and The Force Awakens, and Rise of Skywalker... we just love blowing up Venus.

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.nature.com/articles/srep40063>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.nexusmods.com/skyrim/mods/86932?tab=images>

¹⁵⁰ https://www.icanw.org/report_73_billion_nuclear_weapons_spending_2020

<https://www.nti.org/learn/countries/china/nuclear/>

<https://fas.org/nuke/guide/russia/agency/mo-budget.htm>

<https://www.nti.org/learn/countries/russia/nuclear/>

<https://www.brookings.edu/the-hidden-costs-of-our-nuclear-arsenal-overview-of-project-findings/>

<https://www.brookings.edu/book/atomic-audit/>

<https://armscontrolcenter.org/issues/security-spending/nuclear-weapons-spending/>

<https://chinapower.csis.org/military-spending/>

Estimated Total Nuclear Spending (\$US billions) vs. Country

Figure 8 - with 33% error bars, totals of Nuclear Spending¹⁵¹, based on author's best estimates¹⁵², in \$\$ billions

Please note that China plans to double its nuclear arsenal, although based on Military spending over 21 years, it will take until 2031 to 2062 to catch the current US average (which sadly will either continue to skyrocket, or crash, depending on economic forces).

¹⁵¹ Japan and South Korea do not have weapons, just energy

¹⁵² The estimates for the Us range from \$3 trillion to the cited \$5.5 trillion to a whopping \$13 trillion; so an average is provided. Same for Russia based on a 13% of military spending over a 21 year period, annualized since 1945.

TOTAL & AVG Military Spending 2000-2020 (billions \$\$ adj. inflation)

Figure 9 - Total and Average Military Spending 2000-2021 top 10 countries

Top 10 Military Spending 2000-2020 (billions \$\$ adj. inflation)

Figure 10 - Year by year trends for top 10 countries (log scale) ([non-log scale, no trend line](#))

Figure 11 - USA surpassed by China in 2062? Or 2031? (log scale)

As anyone can see, this is an inordinate amount of money, completely unjustifiable and dangerous. Now, let us again assume that the world is composed of 7.9 billion people. Using 3.5 people per family and \$2,641 in food per year per person¹⁵³ to \$5,055¹⁵⁴ (average of 3.5 people in a home), which is way more than the actual average of the world, one would think, then:

$$\text{Number of years of food} = 7.9 \text{ billion people} * \frac{\$2,641 \text{ food}}{\text{person / year}} * \frac{1}{\$14,734.4 \text{ billion}} = .7 \text{ years worth of food (up to 1.29)}$$

Equation 1: the Food Equation

This number is far different than calculated before, and the author may need to revisit the “Investments in Ragnarok” and improve the paper. But it is still a shocking amount of food.

It may be helpful to point out that it is a large % of GDP, larger than most nations will spend on military for many years.

By any standard, \$14.7 trillion is a lot of money and it may be as high as over \$20 or even \$30 trillion if there are a lot of fudging numbers, or hidden programs. For sure there is some type of extreme paranoia that causes mankind to behave in this way. But where did mankind get the idea that he should or should not apply such power to the surface of the planet?

Mankind was not always thus, and the natives (who professed to not even own the land) do not seem to be inclined in this way. Therefore, we need to understand what in antiquity led to this observation. We only need to re-examine the contents of the previously cited Enuma Elish!

¹⁵³ <https://www.valuepenguin.com/how-much-we-spend-food>

¹⁵⁴ <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/share-of-consumer-expenditure-spent-on-food-vs-gdp-per-capita?tab=table>

The Tablets of Destiny

Looking at lines 41-54,78-80,94,99,105-114,139-142,159-165, & 175 we see a clear story at play.¹⁵⁵ The “power of Anu” - the Tablets of Destiny - were taken by Tiamat and given to Kingu, her consort. This is pre Mars vs. Venus, so that we need not believe this is about Ishtar and Gilgamesh (or Enkimdu/Mercury). This is very likely another body. If not Earth as the author presupposed in “On the Origins of Religions,” then perhaps the goddess Metis which was destroyed by Zeus and became the asteroid belt¹⁵⁶. It could be that the same wind was felt by the Earth, being near. Either way the death was violent, and as it says she was split in two, as we see the two boluses in the asteroid belt. But before that he opens her mouth and fills her with the evil wind.

Figure 12 - the trojan Asteroid Belt ([gif](#)); credit: imgur.com

Why was such a violence associated with the theft of the Tablets? Because the thunderbolt was not only the weapon, but also the power and authority. As we see, Marduk/Jupiter acquired the crown, and therefore the “net” of power to entrap Kingu (and weaken his will), as well as Tiamat. This is all very clearly the electromagnetic force and any gravity is associated with the electrokinetics involved in the remnants of plasma electrical circuits.

But as can be seen, the Tablets of Destiny were a divine right to rule **by force**.

The Peasantry’s Hope for a Holy Grail

What can the peasantry, gentry, gentiles, etc. do about the fact that, ever since the tribes differentiated into chiefs and shamans vs. everyone else in terms of power, authority, and the right to control others’ lives? So far, they’ve done very little, or as in the case of the French Revolution, not knowing what to do with their newfound power, they simply *gave it back* to the nobility¹⁵⁷!

This is because religion, and myth, have both promised a Holy Grail - a chalice of innocent, clean power - which does not involve violence, or even the need to lift a finger (only change your beliefs) to fight against tyranny and give eternal, youthful life. Ironically, this chalice is based upon the cup of the king, which is itself a reference back to the synchrotron shape (see Figure 13). Nevertheless, what chance does the MIMS of religion have against the MIMS of government? Not much, given that since the very first, the two have been literally married. While the chief ran the war and political end, the shaman - often female, sometimes the wives

¹⁵⁵ My lines, not the original.

¹⁵⁶ Also called the Hammered Bracelet

¹⁵⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/event/French-Revolution/The-new-regime>

of the chief - ran the spiritual end, and in this way, certain genes cornered the market on power. And psychologically, it is just such people that always do so. Certain people gravitate towards warriors, police, and soldiers. Some gravitate towards controlling others' lives through softer power. We call these politicians and lawyers. But their origins are in the same genetic lines, the strains which all hearken back to the early chosen few that seem to have much to do with desiring the power to run others' lives.

Figure 13: Chalice: the cup of God; credit: author/A. Peratt

As it happens, the classics do mention that those with Qi in the chest have “bellicosity”¹⁵⁸, that is forcefulness. And the word for strength in Chinese is an arm plasmascript referring back to the Cosmic Hill motif.¹⁵⁹ This word also means force, not *the force*, but as in control or power. But the concept of Qi in the chest is related to Te/De¹⁶⁰, which also means power. Its plasmaglyph is eyes, but earlier, a penis and testicles, which means the plasma streaming between two planets is also associated with male semen, and masculine authority to create life. To create life is also to possibly end life. So the plasma is both seen in giving life and through the weapon taking it. The king is given the sceptre as a cosmic pole, and yet upon it is set the synchrotron shape of the “chalice”, to provide malice with a booming thud upon the floor. This authority is not forgotten to this day. In three scenes in the first Thor movie:

1. King Odin (Figure 14) - pronounced oh-then - slams the spear/sceptre down to silence Thor.
2. Odin uses the spear/sceptre to summon lightning to open the Rainbow Bridge, and then takes Thor’s cosmic hammer, mjolnir - the source of Thor/Mars’ power - from

¹⁵⁸

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/early-china/article/abs/signs-clues-and-traces-anticipation-in-ancient-chinese-political-and-military-texts/BFA26131161A6FB1FA0F9551BD1E4F48>

¹⁵⁹ D. Talbott; see: <http://bit.ly/2BoN0hk>

¹⁶⁰ Note 4, or https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC and https://www.academia.edu/39776252/Ancient_Origins_of_Taijiquan_Do_plasmaglyphics_belle_a_more_ancient_origin_of_the_internal_martial_art_of_Taijiquan_An_EPEMC_Analysis

him until he is worthy. “In the name of my father, and his father before that, I Odin All-Father, cast you out!”¹⁶¹

3. When Thor’s friends come to intercede, Loki quietly, and deftly lets the sceptre hit the ground, and a deep echo resonates when he says “your king.” Though Loki (planet Venus) is no match for the four warriors, the heft of the spear/sceptre warns them against all treason of the magician/warlock Loki’s authority. Note that Loki in myth is occasionally female and the mother of 3 monsters¹⁶², whereas Tiamat is the mother of 12 monsters. Nevertheless, the archetype of women breeding monsters is present, and probably a bastardization of the original myth, clearly related to the Medusa motif.

Figure 15 (gif) - Loki uses Odin’s Sceptre to ignite the Rainbow Bridge with Cosmic Lightning; credit: Marvel

This may seem coincidental, but you don’t have to go very far in looking at the theme of the sceptre, kings, and the grail to find repetitions of religious power, hope, and even electrified comet events. You only need to go to the Arthurian myths which later begat the Renaissance romantic tales! There is no historical fact to King Arthwys¹⁶³ (Arthur II) searching for a Holy Grail.¹⁶⁴ When he crossed into Normandy it was to consolidate the power of Britain, and he went back when Mordred rebelled. He pursued him, and Gwenhyfarr to the north of Wales, where upon catching the adultering couple, had them ripped apart by dogs.¹⁶⁵

But in the romances, after the destruction left by the blight (now known to probably be the 330 AD comet), he either a) goes to Avalon (Anfwynn), which ends up being the Ohio River Valley (via Montreal/St. Lawrence)¹⁶⁶ or b) goes on a quest to cure the world by finding the Holy Grail¹⁶⁷, associated with Jesus Christ, that is a messiah whose appellation refers back to a 2600 BC Egyptian prophecy of the “Christos.”¹⁶⁸ The historical man¹⁶⁹ did fulfill the prophecies, but the fact is these prophecies came out of cosmic references to do with Venus’ attack on Earth.¹⁷⁰

Does the religious MIMS have any power to overthrow the governmental MIMS? Let us also look at the Arthurian histories. His grandfather, Tewdrig (Theodore), murdered his brother in a bid for power¹⁷¹. Again this

¹⁶¹ Planet Jupiter’s father is Saturn/Kronos, and his father before that is Bor/Shamash/Ra/Anu the original star.

¹⁶² “Otherwise, Loki had three children with the female jötunn Angrboða from Jötunheimr; the wolf Fenrir, the serpent Jörmungandr, and the female being Hel. The gods realized that these three children were being raised in Jötunheimr, and expected trouble from them partially due to the nature of Angrboða, but worse yet Loki.” <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Loki>

¹⁶³ 4th Century AD

¹⁶⁴ Same for Arthwyr I of the Roman era, being BC.

¹⁶⁵ As per Wilson & Blackett’s work on the stones and Llandaff Charters. See “Arthur: First King of Britain” & “The King Arthur Conspiracy” for more details.

¹⁶⁶ “King Arthur’s Voyage to the Otherworld,” R. MacCann, 2016

¹⁶⁷ <https://www.bl.uk/onlinegallery/features/mythical/grail.html>

¹⁶⁸ <https://opensiuc.lib.siu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2226&context=ocj>

¹⁶⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A41Tm5FDKns>

¹⁷⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Contendings_of_Horus_and_Seth Here Seth/Set is reenvisioned from the previous age of the Titans (gas giants), by the Old Kingdoms of Egypt. They wanted to imitate the First Kingdoms and later Predynastics and archaics. <https://www.history.com/topics/ancient-history/ancient-egypt>

¹⁷¹ “The Holy Kingdom,” A. Gilbert, 1998; as per Wilson & Blackett

is not common in the peasantry¹⁷², but quite common in nobility. The church there, not a Catholic power but a British form of part-druidic Christianity, then excommunicated Tewdrig for a few years. To ensure he got back into Heaven, as it was believed by most even nobility that one could only make it to the Kingdom if the church pardoned you when you died, he donated land to the church to build a new church upon. They pardoned him, and though his power had not left, it increased afterwards.. This solidifies the High King position - as the Britons had multiple kings who ruled via a “round table” form of Republican Monarchy - and he is able to pass it on to his son Muerygg, and thence to his son Arthwyss (Arthur II).

However, as peaceful as this sounds, it involved murder (fratricide), intimidation, and very deft political machinations of the chief family of the Khumry/Britons of the time. It had nothing to do with peace, or “turning the other cheek.” The People have simply continued to give a pass to the government, no matter how much violence or death is involved. This has continued up into the modern days. While the good people hope in pacifism and religion¹⁷³, the bloodlines of power¹⁷⁴ and aggression hope in the authority of the divine promise of “victory through violence.” Socialists (and Marxists in general) took note in the 1800s. They banished religion, and said “bring on the violence.”¹⁷⁵

Government Breeds War

The truth about this problem is that “government” is the problem. The American solution was the first to turn government upon itself, but after 250 years government has managed to find a way to get around a single tier “checks and balances” system: through socialist programs and endless alphabet bureaucracies¹⁷⁶, simply invent a new, unelected government of basically unstoppable fascist power, corruption, and breed a new nobility. At the top of the hierarchy of this gentry and literati turned nobility is a de facto elite of monetized familial and oligarchical power. Since 2020 began, this elite has consolidated its power, robbed the middle class (gentry), crushed the “expendable” lower class (peasantry), especially abusing minorities and those of disenfranchisement while supporting “useful idiots”¹⁷⁷ who (as they are uneducated) react with chaotic, anarchist rage against those they can reach: other peasants, in order to stoke fear.

There is nothing new about this divide and conquer strategy. In Africa, the colonial powers had a mere 3,000 men and were able to control an entire continent through fear¹⁷⁸, and turning the racism of tribes upon one another¹⁷⁹. As the colonial powers left, they left this hatred behind, and events such as Rwanda¹⁸⁰, or Darfur¹⁸¹ followed. Without the authority of the governmental powers, the populace resorted to the use of violence and rage. If some tribal groups had had nuclear power - if there had really been a “Wakanda”^{182 183} -

¹⁷² Petty people murder for petty reasons; eg:

<https://fox5sandiego.com/news/man-stabs-brother-after-fighting-over-tv-remote/> & again
<https://meaww.com/16-year-old-boy-arrested-fatal-stabbing-older-brother-argument-tv-remote-control>

¹⁷³ Much has been said on the “Opium of the masses.” turns out Marxism is the “Opium of the Literati”
https://monoskop.org/images/7/73/Aron_Raymond_The_Opium_of_the_Intellectuals.pdf

¹⁷⁴ Think: Rothschilds and Rockefellers.

¹⁷⁵ Sadly, it is a pathogenic problem we still have not been rid of even after 100+ million deaths! Look at this devout Communist excuse Stalin and Mao, and even laud their leadership: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lov6jyfKtRc>

¹⁷⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alphabet_agencies

¹⁷⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y9TviluXPSE>

¹⁷⁸ <https://voxeu.org/article/how-colonial-railroads-defined-africa-s-economic-geography>

¹⁷⁹ “Guns, Germs, and Steel,” J. Diamond, 1997

¹⁸⁰ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-13431486>

¹⁸¹ <https://hnh.org/library/research/genocide-in-darfur-guide/>

¹⁸² <https://medium.com/@Mr.Write/but-im-not-racist-wakanda-the-spear-the-shield-the-anatomy-of-trust-f513f736110d>

¹⁸³ You cannot make anyone happy...

<https://kifkif.be/cnt/artikel/15-reasons-why-black-panther-nationalist-xenophobic-colonial-and-racist-movie-6036>

then they would have wiped out **millions**. As it stands they just took the “foreign aid” of western governments¹⁸⁴, and kept their populations starving¹⁸⁵, exposed to disease, unclean water, and war.

There is, though, no need to go to Africa, when we can look at the unfortunate history of said limited and enlightened Federal Government of The United States of America. Since it was corporatized¹⁸⁶ after the Civil War due to its debts to the Rothschild Bank of England¹⁸⁷, here is a fairly complete list of wars and conflicts the United States government has been involved in¹⁸⁸ (excluding riots, massacres, and strikes), and the total expected costs, where [easily] known:

List of American Wars since the Civil War

- Native Wars - multiple¹⁸⁹ \$35 million
- Black Hills War (1867-1877)
- First Korean Conflict (1871)
- Modoc War (1872-1873) \$400,000
- Hawaii (1887-1895) ~\$10 million including purchase
- Garza Revolution¹⁹⁰ (1891-1893)
- Samoan Civil War (1898-1899)
- Spanish-American War (1898) \$283 million¹⁹¹
- Philippine-American War (1899-1902)
- Moro Rebellion (1899-1913)
- Boxer Rebellion (1899-1901)
- Mexican Border Wars (1846-1848 & 1910-1919) \$2.7+ billion¹⁹²
- Banana Wars/Nicaragua (1912-1933)
- Mexico (1914)
- Haiti (1915-1934)
- World War I (1914-1918) \$20 billion
- Russian Civil War (1918-1920)
- Coal (civil) Wars - multiple¹⁹³
- World War II (1941-1945) \$296 billion
- First Indochina War (1946-1954)
- Korean War (1950-1953) \$30 billion
- Laotian Civil War (1953-1975)
- Lebanon (1958)

¹⁸⁴ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/SB123758895999200083>

¹⁸⁵ <https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/pwks6.pdf>

¹⁸⁶ <https://freedom-school.com/history/the-corporation.pdf>

¹⁸⁷ “(15) “United States” means—

(A) a Federal corporation;

(B) an agency, department, commission, board, or other entity of the United States; or

(C) an instrumentality of the United States.” Organic Act of 1871

http://web.archive.org/web/20060708190425/http://assembler.law.cornell.edu/uscode/html/uscode28/usc_sec_28_000030_02----000-.html

¹⁸⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_armed_conflicts_involving_the_United_States

¹⁸⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/American_Indian_Wars

¹⁹⁰ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1051845>

¹⁹¹ <https://www.history.navy.mil/research/library/online-reading-room/title-list-alphabetically/c/costs-major-us-wars.html>

¹⁹² <https://www.usatoday.com/story/money/2019/06/13/cost-of-war-13-most-expensive-wars-in-us-history/39556983/>

¹⁹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coal_Wars

● Bay of Pigs, Cuba (1961)	\$46 million ¹⁹⁴
● Congo (1964)	
● Vietnam War (1963-1975)	\$111 billion
● Thailand (1965-1983)	
● Korean Conflict 3 (1966-1969)	
● Dominican Republic (1965-1966)	
● Bolivia (1966-1967)	
● Cambodia (1967-1975)	
● South Zaire (1978)	
● Afghanistan 1 (1979)	
● Iran (1980)	
● Libya (1981, 1986, 1989, 2011, 2015-present)	\$896 million ¹⁹⁵ + \$2 billion <i>per day</i> ¹⁹⁶
● Lebanon (1982-1984)	
● Grenada (1983)	
● Panama (1989-1990)	
● Gulf War (1990-1991)	\$61 billion
● Iraq No-fly Zone (1991-2003)	\$1-\$2 billion <i>per year</i> ¹⁹⁷
● Somalia (1992-1995) & (2007-present)	
● Bosnia (1992-1995)	
● Haiti (1994-1995)	
● Kosovo (1998-1999)	
● Sudan (1998)	
● Nepal (2002-2006)	
● Afghanistan 2 & Pakistan (2001-2021)	\$2.26 trillion ¹⁹⁸
● Maghreb (2002-present)	
● Horn of Africa (2002-present)	
● Iraq War (2003-2011)	\$1.1 trillion ¹⁹⁹ - \$2 trillion ²⁰⁰
● Indian Ocean Shield (pirates) (2009-2016)	
● Uganda (2011-2017)	
● ISIS (2014-present)	\$14.3 billion ²⁰¹
● Syria (2014-present)	\$40.5 billion ^{202 203}
● Yemen (2015-present)	

¹⁹⁴ <https://www.npr.org/2011/04/17/135444482/50-years-later-learning-from-the-bay-of-pigs>

¹⁹⁵

https://www.washingtonpost.com/blogs/checkpoint-washington/post/libya-war-costs-for-us-896-million-so-far/2011/08/23/gIQA5KplYJ_blog.html

¹⁹⁶ <https://www.cnn.com/2012/10/23/politics/fact-check-libya-cost/index.html>

¹⁹⁷ <https://warontherocks.com/2016/10/political-airpower-part-i-say-no-to-the-no-fly-zone/>

¹⁹⁸ <https://fortune.com/2021/08/18/cost-of-afghanistan-war-time-casualties-deaths-money/>

¹⁹⁹

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Financial_cost_of_the_Iraq_War#:~:text=Direct%20costs,-A%20Marine%20Corps&text=The%20costs%20of%20the%202003,totaled%20just%20over%20%241.1%20trillion.

²⁰⁰

<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-iraq-war-anniversary/iraq-war-costs-u-s-more-than-2-trillion-study-idUSBRE92D0PG20130314>

²⁰¹ <https://dod.defense.gov/OIR/>

²⁰² <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/mideast/RL33487.pdf>

²⁰³ as much as the budget of a top 10 military country per year to fix a problem created by a \$2 trillion war/failure

- Persian Gulf Crisis 2 (2015-present)
- Korean Presence \$4.5 billion *annually*
- Japan Presence \$5.7 billion *annually*

As you can see, war is *expensive*. It has likely always been so. But where did real war (as a government program) actually start, and when? If we can understand why such a MIMS was created, or divined, perhaps we will be capable of understanding what has happened in the world, and to understand disasters like the War on Terror, particularly the Afghanistan theatre.

And what is the resulting benefit of these wars? The following are a series of maps of the expanding US Empire presence, the current US base and reach /territories, and comparisons to previous world empires. You will see that war was a MIMS that is an anti-MIMS, except in that it acquired land and resources (materials) at great human costs.^{204 205}

Figure 16 - US Territorial Expansion via purchases and the Indian Wars (gif); credit: Smithsonian²⁰⁶

²⁰⁴ The Syrian civil conflict and ISIS, etc. have decreased child life expectancy by **13 years** on average, in only the 10 years since it has started. <https://reliefweb.int/report/syrian-arab-republic/too-high-price-pay-cost-conflict-syrias-children>
²⁰⁵ None of this straight talk excuses what the Biden Administration has done in exiting Afghanistan, knowing what would happen, and how they did it: abandoning 30,000 Americans without promise of evacuation. <https://www.businessinsider.com/wh-says-thousands-of-americans-are-still-stuck-in-kabul-2021-8> & <https://www.wbaltv.com/article/afghanistan-1-500-americans-may-still-await-evacuation/37398140>
²⁰⁶ <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/170-years-of-americas-evolution-in-one-animated-gif-12784190/>

US military presence overseas

Figure 19 - US Military Presence Map

Figure 20 - SOCOM Map; credit: thenation.com

We can assume that there is a commensurate naval presence of territorial waters and capabilities (along with control of shipping lanes).

Figure 21 - World Empires in History ~400-500CE ([gif](#))

Figure 22 - Mongol Empire 1200s CE ([gif](#))

Consider now the endless shifting of these empire boundaries throughout history²⁰⁸. It boggles the mind to consider the amount of politics, and the number of lives crushed, destroyed, ruined, and the children and women abused and killed over these thousands of years of unenlightenment. And that just as mankind is achieving the PEMF, because these abuses and trauma are not redressed and dealt with, it actually *accelerated* in the 20th Century... even after the advent of the American Experiment into “fundamental, God-given, human rights!”²⁰⁹

In fact, the only reason for a general peace, however tentative and threatened by COVID tyranny^{210 211} and Cultural Civil Wars right now²¹², is the ridiculous expenditure on US military and NATO presence worldwide. UN and EU peacekeeping forces are completely inept²¹³. And as we have seen in Afghanistan, the moment the Allies leave, the chaos and ritualized death resumes, government attacks government, and 20 years of progress gets wiped away in a sea of vengeance and religious hatred²¹⁴. It is like ISIS all over again²¹⁵, but with a Vietnam War ending²¹⁶. What will happen next, no one precisely knows and it’s clear the generals of the Pentagon do not know, either.²¹⁷

Why does this keep happening? What are the possible origins of war? What do we know, and when did it begin?

The Origins of War

From what we can tell, real war first began in the Peruvian area, 7kya. This is the 7kya Jovian reign boundary. What were the conditions that led to this? Probably, as usual, territorial access to resources (it’s a mountainous area), and racial or tribal tensions. As was seen in Africa in the Zulu Wars, the practice of most tribes had been small-scale, almost demonstrative wars, but this time it was different. This time, they (Tacna? Chinchorro²¹⁸?) were out for blood.²¹⁹ From this period forward, we see a sparse but exponential increase in the behavior of warfare, until the first recognized forms of ancient warfare of Mesopotamia break out at the 2700 BC boundary²²⁰, again this being the Venus-Mars conflict boundary period, as per Velikovsky.

Why did mankind assume that the gods meant for us to have war? Was it that it was inspirational? Or was it that one tribe refused to change gods, or since there was a pantheon of gods and demigods they worshiped different bodies? This would obviously be offensive; maybe more so than even today where even trivial differences in Islamic sects²²¹ lead to brutal bloodshed and terrorism²²². Worshipping completely different

²⁰⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-6Wu0Q7x5D0> 19 minutes long!

²⁰⁹ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/locke-political/>

²¹⁰ <https://www.trtworld.com/video/tv-shows/liberty-or-tyranny-vaccine-passports-are-coming/6079776c3b0f87001e8df323>

²¹¹

<https://www.politifact.com/factchecks/2021/aug/25/facebook-posts/proximity-monitors-wash-school-are-vaccinated-stud/>

²¹² https://www.upi.com/Top_News/Voices/2021/06/30/Harlan-Ullman-American-politics-rational/3071624717263/

²¹³ <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/nov/01/un-failed-to-protect-civilians-in-south-sudan-report-finds>

²¹⁴ <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/row/IF10604.pdf>

²¹⁵ <https://www.bbc.ca/news/world/isis-k-afghanistan-taliban-security-threat-1.6153177>

²¹⁶ <https://japan-forward.com/the-fall-of-kabul-a-tragedy-worse-than-saigon-a-warning-japan-cant-ignore/>

²¹⁷ <https://www.nationalreview.com/2021/08/milley-and-austin-should-resign/>

²¹⁸ Mummification seems to make them a likely candidate for an Egyptian like belief system

<https://www.smithsonianmag.com/travel/fascinating-afterlife-perus-mummies-180956319/>

²¹⁹ <https://www.frommers.com/destinations/peru/in-depth/history>

²²⁰ <https://www.worldhistory.org/war>

²²¹

<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2015/apr/05/sunni-shia-why-conflict-more-political-than-religious-sectarian-middle-east>

²²²

<https://www.history.com/news/sunni-shia-divide-islam-muslim>

spheres would possibly be grounds for genocide and ethnic cleansing! The Olmec and tribes of Costa Rica had different spheres made... did they tolerate pantheism as do modern Hindus, or did they fight if anyone placed different emphasis upon different sized spheres? This would be problematic since the spheres were moving and changing orbital radii and proximity to the Earth, almost at random even during the LaGrange Stability.

Figure 23 - Giant Stone spheroid in Costa Rica. DR ~10.5:8.5 or 1.23, which matches the Ramesses Stele and other Shamash stones²²³; credit: Tico Times²²⁴

Had mankind forgotten the trials of the cataclysms and forgotten the humility of the Deluge? Instead of helping one another like a post-Fukushima earthquake situation, did they immediately go into resource-poor materialistic aggressiveness? Looking at Mesopotamia, it seems likely so, because while the gods are clearly repetitions of each other, the city-states continually conquer one another²²⁵ throughout the fertile crescent for over 2,000 years²²⁶. Now all that remains are a few late ziggurats, and some piles of dust and clay. It is as

²²³ Most Costa Rican stones are 1.02-1.3, or 1.0 exactly. Preliminary results show that there are accurate DR : DR to show that Mars and Venus are present in the triplicates (so not gas giants), with a ratio of 0.57, whereas the actual is 0.56 https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/planetary/factsheet/planet_table_ratio.html

²²⁴ <https://ticotimes.net/2014/06/23/mysterious-stone-spheres-granted-unesco-world-heritage-status>

²²⁵ <https://www.historyonthenet.com/mesopotamian-warfare-the-sumerians-akkadians-and-babylonians>

²²⁶ https://piccionep.people.cofc.edu/graphics/mesop_chronol.html

though war drained the land itself, and created the climate changes... although we know it came from orbital motion and cosmic changes in the PEMS, and even terraforming of the Sahara.²²⁷

Imagine, too, the forced war from the 7kya boundary changes to the Sahara. If there were great civilizations in many of these deserts in the band surrounding the planet, they are wiped out now. Their people displaced, and like the “Sea Peoples,”²²⁸ they would be migrating anywhere they could. Even in the Bible, the Hebrews are driven from Egypt by the Venus catastrophes²²⁹, and after losing one war with Amelykites²³⁰, come to the Promised Land²³¹, and fight war there to take from the inhabitants. David is a conqueror, not a peace-keeper.

The Hebrew government then established an enlightened rule of law based on philosophy centered on monotheism, and all sacred rites once again belong only to the priestly (rabbi) caste. They establish the Holy of Holies²³², and control the wealth, and the line of David holds a literal Divine Right to Rule “covenant” with Je’ho’vah (YHVH) or Jove, aka Jupiter. This precludes them from Sin (moon worship²³³) and the idols (especially the golden calf, or Venus²³⁴), and it promises them government over the world. As it happens the descended Jews inherit the greatest IQ in the world²³⁵, and do currently govern much of it from a banking and media perspective. From MIMS we see the advantage of Zionism: it connects to the G, L, and A powers... but also we see in Solomon a culture with a value for some maths, and for wisdom. Nevertheless, what never, ever leaves Judeo-Christianity is the shadow of war.²³⁶

²²⁷ Our best candidate for the Richat is still the Moon. See “Megafauna Extinction,” Part 4

²²⁸ https://www.worldhistory.org/Sea_Peoples/

²²⁹ “10 Plagues of Egypt”

²³⁰ Book of Exodus

²³¹ Book of Numbers

²³² <https://www.learnreligions.com/the-holy-of-holies-700111>

²³³ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Sin-Mesopotamian-god>

²³⁴ Imagine a learned Egyptian Priest, Moshe, descending from Sinai having been enlightened by the A power and G power, only to find people ripping out hearts and having sex with little boys, as they worship a golden calf idol! Of course he was angry.

²³⁵ <http://web.mit.edu/fustflum/documents/papers/AshkenazilQ.jbiosocsci.pdf>

²³⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Crusades>

MIMS 2.8 - War, the anti-MIMS

War is, as was shown, expensive. Not only in literal costs but in the costs of lives, future progress, human energy and momentum, and economic development. Therefore, it is antithetical to material wealth and fortune. Oscar Schindler made millions through war profiteering, but upon seeing what was happening in the Holocaust, spent his entire fortune to secret out Jews from Germany.²³⁷ He went broke and was still unable to put a dent in the Final Solution.²³⁸ Yet he did more than most members of the Nazi Party. Most people were too afraid to stand up to the government. Why is it that something which everyone knows is so destructive, is believed to be “good for a nation”?

Figure 24 “Be This Guy” (August Landmesser²³⁹); credit Business-Insider²⁴⁰

Note that it is always the nobility and ruling class - lawyers, bankers, and politicians - who are pushing this propaganda. Creedence Clearwater Revival had this to say in “Fortunate Son” (abridged):

*“Some folks are born made to wave the flag
They’re red, white and blue
And when the band plays “Hail to the Chief”
They point the cannon at you, Lord
It ain’t me, it ain’t me
I ain’t no senator’s son, son
I ain’t no fortunate one
Yeah, some folks inherit star-spangled eyes*

²³⁷ <https://www.biography.com/activist/oskar-schindler>

²³⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Final-Solution>

²³⁹ <https://www.businessinsider.com/the-lone-german-man-who-refused-to-give-hitler-the-nazi-salute-2015-6>

²⁴⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/August_Landmesser

*They send you down to war
And when you ask 'em, "How much should we give?"
They only answer, "More, more, more"
It ain't me, it ain't me
I ain't no military son, son
I ain't no fortunate one, one"²⁴¹*

Why do we tell young men that it is fortunate to go to war, when it clearly isn't?²⁴² More curiously, why do young men *feel* it is fortunate to go to war?²⁴³ Why do middle-aged men often feel regret that they did not get a chance to die in a war?²⁴⁴ In "13 Assassins" the head samurai says this upon hearing of the wickedness of a certain ruthless daimyo (who is generally above reproach because he is guarded by overly faithful samurai):

*"How fate smiles on me.
As a samurai in this era of peace...
I've been wishing for a noble death.
Now fate has called me here.
See, my hands...
They won't stop trembling.
It's a warrior's battle shakes.
I will accomplish your wish...
with magnificence."²⁴⁵*

As a martial artist himself, the author identifies with this sentiment. Is it a biological (and therefore electrical) urge, or is there a teaching that is psychologically rooted in a deep cultural DNA? Watching *Gladiator*, or *Braveheart*, or *The Patriot*, or any number of war films, with or without heavy gods' motifs, one cannot help the phenomenon is primarily masculine²⁴⁶, and primarily driven by a desire for **close combat**. In the modern *Jack Ryan* series, based around Tom Clancy's novels and characters, a young drone flight attendant begins to get desperate having killed an incorrect target from afar. He feels cowardly and depressed. This is of course based on a real phenomenon that only appeared since the War on Terror began in 2003. It is the opposite result to what those in the 2001 "Horse Soldiers" squad felt when they went into intimate war to fight enemy combatants in Afghanistan, post 9/11.²⁴⁷ Or what the Doolittle flying squadron felt flying and bombing Japan's heartland after Pearl Harbor, knowing full well they would bail out in the ocean or in China, and potentially become POWs²⁴⁸.

²⁴¹ <https://www.musixmatch.com/>

²⁴²

https://minds.wisconsin.edu/bitstream/handle/1793/76840/Cropsey_Garrett_2017%20Spring_Hist489.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y

²⁴³ <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/gender/2019/04/23/what-really-draws-men-to-war/>

²⁴⁴ <https://msrc.fsu.edu/news/msrcs-david-rudd-consulted-why-modern-soldiers-are-more-susceptible-suicide>

²⁴⁵ https://sublikescript.com/movie/13_Assassins-1436045

²⁴⁶ <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/full/10.1086/711622>

²⁴⁷

<https://www.militarytimes.com/news/your-military/2019/10/18/how-the-horse-soldiers-helped-liberate-afghanistan-from-the-taliban-18-years-ago/>

²⁴⁸

<https://www.defense.gov/Explore/Features/story/Article/2148287/doolittle-raid-on-japan-78-years-ago-buoyed-american-spirits/>

It is a curious axis of purpose vs. shame and guilt. This, and the sheer difficulty of the task, is why so many recruits opt for trying to become Navy SEALs or other spec-ops. They do not want to fight from a distance. They want close personal combat.

In “Sumo: Ancient Ritual to the Thunder God”²⁴⁹ the author explored how hand to hand combat on the dohyo contained many Mars-Venus archetypes. Could the wrestling of Anu and Allalu, of Zeus and Kronos, of Zeus and Typhon²⁵⁰, of Thor and Loki, etc. have inspired a cultural connection? Or is it the chimp brain, which is just more violent than other apes and monkeys? Does this violence give us an extreme evolutionary advantage?

It does appear so.

But modern war is, as stated, disconnected, and controlled rigidly by powerful elites, often family oligarchs, certainly a technocracy of well connected financial moguls. They don’t desire to win (like Vietnam, or Afghanistan), or they would let the soldiers win²⁵¹. They desire military contracts²⁵². President (and general) Eisenhower warned of the Military Industrial Complex.

An Industrial Nation, Steeped in Blood

Now we begin to explore what has been hinted above, the American Empire, or rather more accurately - since America is an ideal and an empire of it would be an empire of the mind rather than borders and bases - the Empire of the U.S.A.®. How has this incorporated, and fully monetized empire reliant on the naval jurisdiction and Uniform Corporate Code (UCC) come about? Was it a socialist takeover? No! Rather, it was a strange motion of four currents. See the following table:

Table 2 - 4 Currents of American Dominance

Current	Major Events	Major Outcomes
Great Enlightenment (second Renaissance, but in America)	Declaration of Independence, American Revolution,	Cultural dominance of the West in 19th and 20th centuries, atomic theory and bomb, space and genetic exploration
Industrialization	Transcontinental Railroad, Civil War, invention of cars, AC current, modern world, etc.	Rise of the Corporation over Agricultural Economy; accelerating dissolution of the religious nuclear family value system
Revivalism	Puritan and Quaker idealist expansion westward Example: the Billy Graham Crusade	Western Missionary expansion and pseudo-colonialism of the entire globe
Territorial Expansions	Indian and Banana Wars, Purchases of large territories, Alaska and Hawaii especially	Foundations of resource access for world’s greatest empire

²⁴⁹ Ibid. pp. 6,11-12

²⁵⁰ <https://www.greek-gods.info/greek-gods/zeus/stories/zeus-typhoon/>

²⁵¹ “John Rambo: Sir, do we get to win this time? Trautman: This time it's up to you.” ~First Blood Part 2

²⁵² <https://newrepublic.com/article/163323/afghanistan-war-military-industrial-complex-scam>

These currents were all very powerful, very fast overall - and still accelerate in many cases - and so necessitate increasing hierarchical and organizational superstructure. That means empire when you talk about large territories. To be organized, you need “lean” law code²⁵³, clear and concise legal apparatus. It means having clear code or instructions about how the country should function, rather than clunky common law. It also means **cost**.

The issue of the increase in a culture’s signal is primarily that it comes at the expense of other cultures’ weaker signals. When you add technology and therefore leverage and position, there is a high likelihood of this advantage to be abused, and when you add Raw Power²⁵⁴, there is a strong likelihood it will be thoroughly corrupting. So the American Experiment really died all the way back at the end of the Civil War, with Lincoln. Almost a distinct ending, since it was he that ended states’ sovereignty at any rate (and for good reasons, and for evil reasons).²⁵⁵ But what blossomed out of the plant that grew from those ashes was something no one expected. A great nation, not yet in ideals of justice (not until 1964 at least), but in casting a shadow upon the world. Like a goliath itself, the nation grew and grew. It weathered, like a mighty boxing champion, crashes in gold markets, booms in oil and stock markets, depressions, and world wars. Of the hidden power within this industrializable behemoth, Yamamoto said in 1941, “I fear all we have done is to awaken a sleeping giant and fill him with a terrible resolve.”

The US is a nation versed in continual warfare, almost like some Spartan type nation, but powered by direct access to the entire “big G” on a cultural level, and altogether disinterested in old world beliefs which hold it back. Even the religion of Christianity which flourished in that period 1700s - 1900s was dominated by a secular and evolved fervor to the New Testament, not so much the Old. There was a freshness to it, which only until recently as the Asiatic signal began to outpace (due to IQ asset dominance²⁵⁶), and with the help of the West itself (see pseudo-colonialism above), seemed ever self-reviving. Of course, now with the extremes of fiscal divide, obesity, medical deprivation, moral perversion, injustice, and political (fascist) corruption, this signal struggles. It is not clear that the movement is back towards that American Experiment, either, for not all the populism from 2016-2020 has been purely patriotic. It has been mixed with racial nationalism²⁵⁷, nation-building, and is beginning to be more rooted in anti-European signals. This does not support some of the roots. Nevertheless, it is too early to tell. The fact remains that the four currents did create a government which had in it the seeds and power to go far. Far too far.

Any government that can essentially ask its friends in banking to continually feed it money²⁵⁸, and violate the laws of thermodynamics, can justify seemingly infinite expansion. Such a government will also purchase large amounts of military equipment, and such a stockpile of militaristic pulse will lead to bellicosity. America is nothing if not a bellicose nation. It is brash, arrogant, and increasingly uneducated²⁵⁹. The result in such cases is not that people cannot use technology for leverage. It is that when they do, or when they are told what to do and what to think about it, they will do so without considering weighing the responsibility of freedom against the responsibility to refrain from tyranny.

²⁵³ Although, the cost of this is excessive verbosity. Law at the start of America could be read by an 8th grader. Now it is written at the reading equivalent of a 16th grader. Lawyers often need lawyers to explain modern, corporate made “laws” such as the 2,000 page Infrastructure Bill, or 906 page Obamacare. The Congress itself needs help just to understand what it is told to pass, so they can read it! <http://www.gpo.gov/fdsys/pkg/BILLS-111hr3590enr/pdf/BILLS-111hr3590enr.pdf>

²⁵⁴ “Axioms of Power,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2019

²⁵⁵ What hadn’t died yet ended (in terms of freedom) with racist gun control laws, Income Tax, Social Security, Selective Service, etc. These were the trappings of the modern industrialized world to come.

²⁵⁶ https://www.academia.edu/50652106/China_vs_the_World_IQ_as_a_Strategic_Asset_a_graphical_comparison

²⁵⁷ Far too much has been said to insinuate anti-Asian bias, but studies show 87% of new violence (which is already statistically negligible), are from left voting African Americans. <https://www.nytimes.com/2010/05/02/us/02sfcrime.html>

²⁵⁸ <https://www.investopedia.com/can-u-s-states-declare-bankruptcy-4843140>

²⁵⁹ <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2017/02/15/u-s-students-internationally-math-science/>

When America loses itself, the world will also follow.²⁶⁰ The “tree of liberty” has a shadow side of a “weed of tyranny.” People hate tyrants. The Romans said “sic semper tyrannis” as they stabbed their Caesars. What will the world say to the Superpower, if it falls out of itself, like Kronos, into a mad titan, eating children? It will say “You are not King. You are a failed God.”

The Rise of The Superpower

“The superman exists, and he’s American,” ~Watchmen²⁶¹

Figure 25: Dr. Manhattan; credit: A.Moore/DC comics

Of gods, and of men, ever has the government been driven by such a fascination. We make fun of Hitler for his occult researches and expenditures, but actually the CIA, the Soviets, all governments have always (and maybe always will) dabble into the mysteries and metaphysique. Partially because it is good science, and fulfills our hypothesis (III)²⁶², but also because governments love wasting money on either silly research and pseudo-science, or upon pranking the public²⁶³ with it (like UFOs^{264 265}).

But there is nothing occult about atomic power.

It was not a light decision that Harry S. Truman made to be the first, and God-willing, only world leader to choose to use an atomic weapon upon a defenseless populace. He did so only because of the dominant signal driving America forward against an implacable enemy that represented the old world Shinto/animistic beliefs in the gods. Their emperor was literally a god on Earth.²⁶⁶ They would *not* surrender. In fact they’d kill the god before killing themselves at the “end of the world.” Fortunately that didn’t happen, and McArthur made sure that the emperor surrendered voluntarily and completely/unconditionally. However before that would happen, America unleashed two devastating weapons of the gods (and at that time the only two), upon Hiroshima and Nagasaki: manufacturing ports for the Japanese navy. The European theatre had already ceased and the Soviets were trying to reposition towards the Pacific theatre. The Americans had to move quickly, and they also did not want to lose thousands in a costly invasion to the main island. Island hopping had been excessively brutal as it was.

²⁶⁰ <https://www.pri.org/stories/2019-04-03/america-has-been-nato-s-helm-70-years-can-it-survive-without-us-leadership>

²⁶¹ In reference to Dr. Manhattan, a product of tachyon experimentation with electricity in the 1950s, creating an alternate reality where Richard Nixon remained president throughout the Cold War 1980s. Manhattan is a direct reference to the Manhattan Project, and the character has a symbol of Hydrogen upon his Yin Tang or 3rd Eye. He is, in fact a god, and probably actually stronger than the more positivist Jewish messiah archetype, “Superman” which was created in the 1930s.

²⁶² https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions pp. 15-16, 23

²⁶³ <https://nymag.com/news/features/conspiracy-theories/false-flags/>

²⁶⁴ <https://www.nytimes.com/1997/08/03/us/cia-admits-government-lied-about-ufo-sightings.html>

²⁶⁵ <https://fas.org/sgp/library/ciafo.html>

²⁶⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emperor_of_Japan

The result: to launch America into the pantheon of Heracleian gods. Ares himself hadn't shown this kind of power since before Socrates... and no one on this Earth had witnessed that kind of power save the cultures destroyed by volcanoes like Pompeii.

None had in an era post electricity, with recording, magnetic storage and radio to reach the whole world.

What followed was the unfortunate development of the Cold War, with the Soviets catching up, and the two nations launched into an unprecedented era of nuclear testing, irradiating the world, altering the PEMS, and setting up conditions of potential worldwide destruction.²⁶⁷

Figure 26 - Animated Map of Nuclear Tests 1948-1998; credit: PopularMechanics

Fortunately, this testing has slowed or even in many cases stopped. People (even the rank and file nobility, the warmongers) recognize the insanity of nuclear war and “Mutually Assured Destruction.”²⁶⁸ They might not extend this to their own religion to authority, nor ever question their devotion to propagandizing their peasants, gentry, and training literati on how to recirculate these beliefs about the “good of war.” But they do see *limit*. That is a form of progress.

So what now? Actually the Universe deals with such excesses and eccentricities quite elegantly. It either lets them peter out through massive boom/bust/famine type cycles (such as deer populations exploding and eating all the food, then dying out). Or it finds ways to tip balance away, to erode concentrations of charge and power, and distribute them; the purpose of gradients.

But... this is a major concern. Not only because you do not want a distribution of WMDs, especially not in the era of CRISPr machines and the plethora of access to cheap explosive household products, but because any redistribution of state assets necessarily means the economic decline²⁶⁹, and so poverty, and so crime, misery and deprivation of the human soul (lack of material sustenance, etc.), and an ever closer march to a de facto “end of the world!”

Considering mankind's obsession with this end, psychologically and patho-socially, mankind cannot afford even one “Broken Arrow” or “Sum of All Fears.” Not. Even. One.

²⁶⁷ <https://www.thejournal.ie/ozone-layer-damage-depletion-nuclear-testing-danny-healy-rae-3057410-Nov2016/>

²⁶⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/mutual-assured-destruction>

²⁶⁹ Think: Soviet Union or buffer states, like Tajikistan. Would you trust their government with even the smallest dirty bomb material? That's why it was so disappointing that although the Neocons toppled tyrant Saddam Hussein, he did not even have WMD materials like “yellowcake” and it totally destabilized the region. This suited the NWO, but not the real World Order. War profiteering came at the cost of simplicity and stability, and literal cost. That money could have been used for much better projects. But also, now no one will trust “the boy who cried wolf” even when the wolf (inevitably) appears.

And to the Republic, For Which it Stands...

So where should the loyal American stand? For the Republic “for which it stands,” or for the teetering, Pisa-like “world order” which has abused the superpower status, for profits of individuals and cabals of elitists? It is sad because growing fear or loathing of the American federal government and its empire has been conflated with the American Experiment. But also, it has caused even Americans themselves to question God, country, family values²⁷⁰, liberty²⁷¹, and human rights²⁷². It has made them susceptible²⁷³ to the sociopathic socialist pathology, but also unwilling to fight it.^{274 275}

Yet, it is precisely because war is both a necessary MIMS and an anti-MIMS, that it is so axial to study this issue. We are at the crux of it 2019-2024. What is the defining nature of “entheos” - the God Within? What is the American character if it uses liberty and free will to create industrialized warfare and death, merely because that is what the gods did 7kya, 4kya, and 2.7kya?²⁷⁶

We must understand MIMS 2.8 because it is like a loaded firearm in the house. On its own, as a concept, it is nothing dangerous. But in the hands of the ignorant [child, as mankind is] it can create manslaughter or suicide. It not only can, it will. It will be like Newton’s apple: decisive.

No Nation that Loves War

“There is no instance of a nation benefitting from prolonged warfare.” ~Sun Tzu²⁷⁷

What shall happen to a nation that “loves war” and fights it on multiple fronts? While it was a gold-based economy, and not fiat, we do have the lessons of the Peloponnesian War, and of Thucydides, to indicate to us²⁷⁸. By the end of that war, the Athenians, who had had:

- ❖ The most powerful Grecian city-state
- ❖ The most powerful Navy
- ❖ A republic
- ❖ A military bullied by the Senators (noble class)
- ❖ Extreme cultural arrogance

... were defeated by the Spartans. Their city was burned, and sacked. And rightly so. It was the end of Athens’ first golden era. It led away from an “enlightened”, or scholarly based society, towards a militaristic and extremely conservative empire led by the Spartans. In modern parlance, the end of liberal America, NATO, and the west, and the rise of an Axis: China, Russia, and the Muslim Brotherhood. How did this happen? Primarily, Athens relied too heavily upon a plunder economy, and their navy, and when the war chest would get empty, rather than sticking to their ideals, and having exhausted their taxes, they would start another war.²⁷⁹ So they ended up in battles against:

²⁷⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK56255/>

²⁷¹ <https://www.csmonitor.com/USA/Politics/2021/0701/Why-free-speech-is-under-attack-from-right-and-left>

²⁷² <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2020/country-chapters/united-states>

²⁷³ <https://www.cnbc.com/2018/08/14/fewer-than-half-of-young-americans-are-positive-about-capitalism.html>

²⁷⁴ <https://news.gallup.com/opinion/polling-matters/287459/public-opinion-review-americans-word-socialism.aspx>

²⁷⁵ <https://www.aclu.org/sites/default/files/assets/121013-humanrightsfacts.pdf>

²⁷⁶ That’s not to say any other nation would do better: Russia, China, Israel, Saudi Arabia... they would all do decidedly far more, if they had been the sole superman.

²⁷⁷ Ch 2.6, “The Art of War,” L. Giles, <https://www.sacred-texts.com/tao/aow/aow01.htm>

“2.7. It is only one who is thoroughly acquainted with the evils of war that can thoroughly understand the profitable way of carrying it on.”

²⁷⁸ <https://oll.libertyfund.org/title/hobbes-the-english-works-vol-viii-the-peloponnesian-war-part-i>

²⁷⁹ Sound familiar?

- Sparta
- Corinth
- Persia
- Crete
- Syracuse
- Sicily

Look back at the list of American Wars: how many do you see marked “-present”?

Winning the First Cold War

“But,” you say, “it was American cultural dominance and the ‘outspending’ of the USSR through superior economy, capitalism, and good-old-American know-how which won us the Cold War.”²⁸⁰

Maybe so. And China has learned well from it, and directly from us.²⁸¹ They have a fiat currency on steroids.²⁸² Thankfully it’s less trustworthy than our own! But was it really *our strength* that won the Cold War? Was it really as if the “wind blowing” from our state “bent the grasses” of the Ural and Caucasus plains? Did the steppes feel our “weightiness”? Did our “awesomeness”²⁸³ bowl them over?

Or - more likely - did the USSR collapse due to the faults of Communism²⁸⁴, longstanding cultural issues, especially between huge variations in ethnicity, and due to the failure of a governmental system that contained not even a realistic double tier checks and balances system to control the excesses²⁸⁵ of that MIMS? It was a powerful, centralized state with centralized planning. They put out clear messages to the Universe about what they desired, why, and to what end.

The Universe simply disagreed. The individual constituents of that Soviet System found it an untenable game. Maybe this is keeping up with the USA ® or maybe it was keeping up a race against time. It is potentially likened to a young girl who receives a shopping credit card at age 16. When she starts, she has the allowance to cover the bills. When she exceeds, she opens another credit card to pay the first off, and so on. By the time “daddy” sees the situation, it has ballooned to over \$10,000 or more in credit exposure. That collapse, both spiritually and physically (hopefully not permanently), is sure to be a different line for each system or individual setup. But it will happen at that line and not another day of borrowing from the future will allow it to continue!

²⁸⁰ <https://www.hsdl.org/?view&did=444565>

²⁸¹ “Stealth War: How China Took Over While America’s Elite Slept,” Gen. R. Spalding, 2019

²⁸² Debt:GDP over 300% and rising

<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-china-economy-debt/chinas-debt-tops-300-of-gdp-now-15-of-global-total-iif-idUSKCN1UD0KD>

²⁸³ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23250704>

²⁸⁴ Communism was failing at Jamestown and Plymouth Rock long before Karl Marx ever came around. Well meaning Christians were using “community pots” for food and finding the elite would rob the pot and everyone would starve. The Natives of Massachusetts took pity on the struggling farmers and taught them how to quickly grow corn. But at Jamestown, cannibalism reared its ugly head as food stores depleted. Plenty of game, but enemy tribes all around, and as your energy gets low, people tend to lay about and get worse, instead of working harder to get out of the situation. See: “Bear Grylls: The Island, Season 2,” for the best experiment done on camera to date for this. If Bear had not helped the women, and they’d had radio contact, they would have all died within a few more days to weeks. For 5 weeks they had no hierarchical order, and it wasn’t til week 5 they began to eat well and work together, and have elected leaders.

²⁸⁵ Both the Soviets and China, and of course the Nazis, utilized the Secret Police, KGP, Politburo, etc. This roots out anti-Communism, but that’s not the same thing - indeed it is generally the opposite - as rooting out corruption and debauchery, fraud, etc. After the Cold War many generals and KGB became pimps and drug dealers, and some even sold nuclear materials and weapons. <https://www.cfr.org/background/loose-nukes> & <https://www.nti.org/analysis/articles/loose-nukes-black-market-sales-nuclear-weapons-and-material-russia/>

Ignorance Breeds Arrogance

Whence comes the arrogance that so epitomizes the American zeitgeist which spread pathologically through the Republic after World War II? Was it pure swagger?²⁸⁶ Or something else? According to the Hindu Brahmins, it is dukkha (ignorance-suffering) which is the cause of the false self to arise, and to make the person suffer.

What kind of ignorance makes mankind suffer?

- Ignorance of Causes & Conditions (Outflows)
- Ignorance of Chain of Reaction
- Ignorance of Nonlinear Dynamics' effects on systems
- Ignorance of Codependent Causality
- Ignorance of Positional Advantage/Strategic Configuration of Power²⁸⁷ (lines & fields)
- Ignorance of the Changes
- Ignorance of Self & Dao = No Dao-de²⁸⁸
- Ignorance of what one is ignorant about (mostly the future trends, but also spiritual [dis]connectivity)
- Ignorance of the Laws of God and Universe, etc.
- Ignorance of the Powers & rules of power.²⁸⁹

Due to these kinds of ignorance, mankind suffers from "terminal brain retardation" or "chronic insanity" where insanity is famously defined as "doing the same thing over and over again, expecting different results."

Arrogance Breeds Catastrophe

Psalm 5:5 "The boastful shall not stand in Your sight; You hate all workers of iniquity."

Isaiah 10:5 "Woe to Assyria, the rod of My anger And the staff in whose hand is My indignation."

Ezekiel 33:28 "For I will make the land most desolate, her arrogant strength shall cease, and the mountains of Israel shall be so desolate that no one will pass through."

Zephaniah 2:8 "I have heard the reproach of Moab, And the insults of the people of Ammon, With which they have reproached My people, And made arrogant threats against their borders."

In many instances in history, the arrogant country, king, or general "gets his comeuppance" or "what's coming to him,"²⁹⁰ because people do not like arrogance. More than that, people do not like arrogance that fails. In the case of America - like Rome - the collapse will probably be as intensely disturbing as what

²⁸⁶ <https://www.khanacademy.org/humanities/us-history/postwarera/postwar-era/a/the-baby-boom>

²⁸⁷ https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi

²⁸⁸ <https://bit.ly/3gDITSP> De means "inner power" See: "Original Tao," H. Roth, 1999

²⁸⁹ See: "The 48 Laws of Power," R. Greene, 1998

²⁹⁰ "Tai Gong said: "Make them rich and observe whether they commit offenses. Put him in a high position and see if he becomes arrogant. Entrust him with office and see if he stays. Make him solve a problem and see if he will conceal anything. Put them in the way of danger and see if he is afraid. Task him to manage emergency and see if he is able to handle it well."

"If he is rich but does not commit offenses, then he is benevolent. If he is in a high position but does not become arrogant, then he is righteous. Entrust him with office and he stays, then he is loyal. If he solves the problem without concealing anything, he is trustworthy. If he is in danger and is not afraid, then he is courageous. Task him to manage emergencies and he handles well, he is capable of making plans and strategising. The ruler cannot entrust the three 'treasures' to other people, otherwise he will lose his awesomeness." ~Six Secret Teachings ch6., ctext.org

correlates to the height of power and superiority over the competing nations, neighbors, and empires. All the more so, according to Chinese sciences, because the victory in the Cold War was so openly, socially, and unanimously agreed to come from America's greatness, and not from the total deficiency of the Soviets. This led, almost immediately (actually already since the 1970s) to the force-feeding of a parasitic Communist China. It was foolish, but all empires at their peak are so foolish. The Athenians, the Romans, Alexander, the Aztecs, the Inca, the Qin... all of them were arrogant. All of them failed. All of them began to collapse like a bubble made in cavitation by a mantis shrimp.

When a cavity bubble expands, it generates high heat conditions.²⁹¹ When it collapses, the energy is transferred into kinetic motion. Historically, this has meant looting, burning, raping, pillaging, all the kinds of things seen in Iraq, or at the library of Alexandria, or the fall of Troy. It is a terrible, monstrous thing. But it is a matter of physics, and of history. It is the resultant effect of an anti-MIMS redounding upon an ignorant,

arrogant progenitor of said "goodness" of the MIMS, led by a government where the "tail wags the dog" and the "blind follow hard upon the blind."

Figure 27 - Cavitation Collapse ([gif](#))

From what the author can tell, it is beginning with the collapse of American war strategy. The failure at Vietnam and the buildup of arms, leading to the precipitous heights of Gulf War victory, and later the raging, rending, crushing defeat of Saddam Hussein, and the Taliban/Al

Qaeda, but now in full reversal, the humiliating defeat by Afghani insurgents - country bumpkins - possibly because of China (the tiger who wants wings). This may signal a full scale world tilt in the "Order of Things" that only adds to the COVID tyranny situation, and leads to a cavitation or "black swan event." The author cannot know, or predict the future. So only time will tell.

The Three Body Problem

Where does this leave the state of the world? Looking at Table 1 in "Winning the New Cold War"²⁹² we see that the NATO allies are not so reliable - and neither is the current United States Executive Branch - and Russia's status is slightly antagonistic with a strong possibility to get worse. Discounting the undeveloped world, since IQ analysis shows that India and Brazil are no match for China²⁹³, then this leaves the world in a 3 body problem:

1. The United States and its closely allied but entirely dependent and weak allies
2. The EU/UN "allies" with some axis leanings (Italy, Germany, Greece)
3. The China-Russia axis, with its NWO supporters

Behind the curtain the NWO, Deep State, and various players from communist to fascist to Islamist work to antagonize these three into serious (ie, warm war) opposition.

²⁹¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1350417720303229>

²⁹² Pp. 7

²⁹³ Ibid. pp. 12-13

This, to the author, is a designed scenario, as it is a little too much like the book, “1984” for the author’s comfort. More to the point, though, is that it seems engineered for a perpetual war in the Middle East, as a way to create war profiteering. However, the Universe does not favor this, and the Changes always continue. Three body problems always prove to be unstable, to be unable to maintain. Our obsession with three-legged stools or three-faced gods notwithstanding, the Universe does not care a whit about such ideal “golden ages of the gods.” It didn’t care even when three gas giants came from the same star.²⁹⁴ A fourth player, or fifth including the sun, entered in and the entire system fell into war, and chaos.

That appears to be what would happen here. And agents of chaos bet on that.

World War 3: the Sequel No One Wants

There are certain elites who make ridiculous claims about the “thing America needs is another war.”²⁹⁵ The Project for a New American Century, as has been documented elsewhere, which was a neoconservative group, forged an alliance with pro-war Big Libs like the Clintons and John Kerry et al. to conspire to put America into an endless War on Terror.²⁹⁶ It was known to be endless *at the time* because of the way destroying nation states like Ghaddafi’s Libya or the caliphates in Syria, etc. would lead towards a powder keg of incessant tribal and sectarian violence. Our allies the Kurds suffered the most, and then later the Trump Administration shamelessly abandoned them, and Kurdish female freedom fighters were beheaded on livestream on the internet.²⁹⁷

Meanwhile, the Military Industrial Complex began to see that the war was bad for morale, and we had already developed a modern drone and *software-driven* (emphasis on soft) military. The standards for infantry kept dropping²⁹⁸, and either socialism was invading, or a new line of thinking associated with “how to defeat an enemy as large as China” came to modify US strategy²⁹⁹. The United States, too, was thinking of Total War³⁰⁰ and asymmetrically. In asymmetrical warfare, you want more bodies, not only alpha male bodies. Now the United States mulls over a desire to add women to the Selective Service draft.

What does this mean? A kinder, gentler war-machine? Not likely. It means that the Military Industrial Complex, and their puppets in the Empire at the Pentagon and the NGOs in downtown Washington DC - seeing China is not the grateful vassal they thought they were molding³⁰¹ - actually intend to grow America through immigration of hispanics and Asians in order to gear up and try to make the python swallow the cow. Snakes who try to swallow overly large meals, even Anacondas, find their bellies ripped open and both die. As the Chinese say, “If two tigers fight, one is sure to be injured.”³⁰² They mean killed.

For China’s part, they are patiently awaiting the opportunity to just buy out all the farmland, utilities, water supplies, and votes... and simply own America from the inside out. Like a puppet. This is excellent Art of War.

²⁹⁴

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunberbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

²⁹⁵ <https://www.e-ir.info/2014/06/14/the-neoconservative-influence-on-us-foreign-policy-and-the-2003-iraq-war/>

²⁹⁶ “Hubris: The Inside Story of Spin, Scandal, and the Selling,” M. Isikoff & D. Corn, 2006

²⁹⁷

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2777067/ISIS-behead-five-Kurdish-fighters-including-three-women-severed-head-s-shared-online-terror-fanatics.html>

²⁹⁸ <https://nypost.com/2021/05/11/armys-first-female-infantry-officer-blasts-lower-standards/>

²⁹⁹ <https://www.wsws.org/en/articles/2015/11/03/laws-n03.html>

³⁰⁰ <https://www.dtss.us/blog/pentagon-report-points-to-us-preparations-for-total-war/>

³⁰¹ “Deceiving the Sky,” B. Gertz, 2019

³⁰² 两虎相争，必有一伤 liǎng hǔ xiāng zhēng , bì yǒu yī shāng “if two tigers fight, one must get injured; if you start a war, someone is bound to get hurt” <http://www.standardmandarin.com/>

But they are losing patience, and the yingpai or warhawks, who have no idea what it is like to fight real wars (all being too young to remember World War II), or to fight as bloody and war-obsessed a nation as the USA ® are going to find out that it is not so easy as “rattling the sabre” at Taiwan.

Why Taiwan? Why Afghanistan? Why Venezuela, South Africa, and Libya? Why not Cuba or Zimbabwe or Kazakhstan, etc.?

→ Taiwan

- ◆ TSMC - the world’s **only** complete microchip 0 to 100% complete fabrication facility³⁰³
- ◆ Key industrial centers
- ◆ Jewel of the South China Sea and access to greater Pacific controls

→ Afghanistan

- ◆ Oil pipelines
- ◆ Access to the Poppy fields (medicines)
- ◆ Massive mineral reserves³⁰⁴

→ Venezuela

- ◆ One of the world’s largest oil reserves
- ◆ Also one of the world’s largest mineral reserves

→ South Africa

- ◆ Diamonds
- ◆ Minerals
- ◆ Horn of Africa (strategic pass between Atlantic and Indian Oceans, especially if the Suez Canal collapses in use as it did in 2021³⁰⁵)

→ Libya

- ◆ Large water reserves³⁰⁶
- ◆ Oil
- ◆ Access to the channels of the Mediterranean / ports

The USA ® and its NWO - the Big Tech elite - are thinking about how to control their bottlenecks and chokepoints, and how to remain atop their pyramids at a time when Chinese firms are sneezing their way to the top.³⁰⁷ Many of these American (Silicon Valley and Seattle) firms do not even manufacture hardware.³⁰⁸ They have no leverage to force the Chinese manufacturers to sell to them, nor to control the mines which are needed. Chinese tech companies are catching up (by hook, nook, and thievery) to them with cheap supply and “good enough” quality. Where do they want to sell? In a place where the NATO alliances are weak, and the demand is still high: Africa, Oceania, and Central & South America.³⁰⁹

This type of ancient reason for warfare - resource driven - has more potential mojo behind it than a religious or idealistic crusade, and no matter what can be said of Americans’ (and the West’s) internal desire

³⁰³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AeN3oQx-o68>

³⁰⁴

<https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/other/3-trillion-and-counting-global-players-eyeing-afghanistans-vast-mineral-reserves/ar-AANOUrZ>

³⁰⁵

<https://www.republicworld.com/world-news/africa/ever-given-ship-that-blocked-suez-canal-in-march-crosses-waterway-again.html>

³⁰⁶ https://www.temehu.com/Cities_sites/Gabroun.htm

³⁰⁷ Already 4/5 of the biggest banks of the world are Chinese.

³⁰⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JH2nXMv6yZI> & <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LoTx9LQIKEA>

³⁰⁹ These happen to be the “best places” for human slavery/traffickers as well

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tn_KcWR06l8

for freedom in 2021 - and political machinations dividing this belief up - they sure as Hell do not care a bit if the rest of the world wants it as well.³¹⁰

Nation building has never really worked, not even for the Romans. It is expensive, and the Middle East does not have the mentality of modernization behind its political gears currently as it did in the middle of the 20th Century.³¹¹ It has a mind for fantastical Islamic caliphates and idealistic middle kingdoms. The burthen of the gods? Or centuries and millennia of religious cultism? Regardless, this is an ideal playground for a Military Industrial Complex and endless contracts and intrigues.

But also for the death of useful, expensive intelligence and military and PMC assets. The undeveloped 2nd world has the promise of birth rates, forests, minerals, and no Islam. The powers that be - especially the neo colonizers of China - foresee places remote like Ghana as endless markets. They want to settle the steppes, and establish friendly relations with Eastern Europe, but to finance such a new land-based (rather than sea-based as the USA ® and the UK were) empire would require ore, minerals, oil, manpower (labor), and control of access. China understands encirclement and buffer zones, and they do not like the US naval grip on the South China Sea one bit.

It is for these reasons, therefore, and that since no one wants Mutually Assured Destruction, that the next world war has started in cyberspace³¹², and is rapidly moving into outer space³¹³. Unfortunately, for mankind, the Law of Causality does not care about domains and spheres. It applies in a nonlinear **and** linear fashion, to all domains. How it calculates the resultants is not always clear. But the anti-MIMS of war will suck dry the coffers and purses of imperial powers just as fast in outer space, or faster. Of course, China has realized this (and being over-leveraged already), has moved to control cyberspace and the MIMS (1.2) of cryptocurrency. Already in 2021 they forced out crypto miners, causing a near world economic meltdown when they tanked \$trillions in the market. Fortunately, unlike plummeting stocks, crypto currencies have a trade and holding volume,

Numbers kept all market reshaped, technologies Chinese Imperial is already mostly month turnaround. system of its feeds it there. Can MIMS really offset space warships?

and the power of things afloat. The and new hardened against attack. The market healed, within a 4 It drains the fiat currency, and such a cyberspace the cost of making

Figure 28 (gif) - How Mankind sees Space Wars, as World War II Battleship type fights³¹⁴; credit: Lucasfilm

The author doubts it very much - at least in the 21st and 22nd century

³¹⁰ <https://www.investors.com/politics/commentary/americans-tired-of-mideast-nationbuilding/>

³¹¹ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Iranian-Revolution>

³¹²

<https://www.ida.org/-/media/feature/publications/2/20/2011-cyberspace---the-fifth-operational-domain/2011-cyberspace---the-fifth-operational-domain.ashx>

³¹³ <https://smallwarsjournal.com/jrn/art/space-cyber-and-changing-notions-of-war>

³¹⁴ Which, of course, is ridiculous considering both the cost of such an engineered piece, and how tenuous our existence in space could or would be due to the dangers of space, and ease of destroying life support systems. Movies always gloss over these dangers to focus on the vacuum of space. Vacuum is not the worst concern!

The question is, can a MIMS that converts “fossil fuel”³¹⁵ into the PEMF through “barbarism”³¹⁶ really float such an expansion to attract enough fortune-aether? Probably not. So until we switch to Thorium or the other author-identified energy methods³¹⁷, how much good would it do? And the more burning, the more power socialists & fascists and their lies about climate change³¹⁸ get through to propaganda. How ironic: the stubborn capitalists of Big Oil sow the seeds of their own supplanting. The Communists (especially China) have never been shy about toxic but abundant energy supplies. And they certainly don’t have a problem with lies and propaganda. It is sad to see the Biden Administration kill small oil³¹⁹ and prop up the power of Big Oil (OPEC and Shell, BP, Exxon, etc.)³²⁰, and because of nonlinear effects *give the game away to China*. But the government - probably the world’s worst MIMS ever created - does not learn. It is too busy playing the “game of thrones.”

How War is the anti-MIMS

So this leads us to our conclusive question about this hypothesis for 2.8: how exactly is war an *anti*-MIMS?

When individuals go to war, or defend themselves, or fights between man and woman (or same sex increasingly these days³²¹), it is natural to say “well, destruction begets creation, and sometimes it has to happen.” The author is not a pacifist. He believes in the proper utility of war and of rebellion and civil war. But that is not what we are speaking about in the modern era.

Firstly, whether you believe 9/11 was an “inside job” or not, the fact remains that a) America defended itself against a new terrorist enemy and b) that wasn’t the war the Elite wanted and it quickly moved to the background.³²²

Industrialized, bureaucratically led war and war profiteering is a blight on human economy, futurism, and for this reason many in the altstream think that hyperdimensional aliens or ancient alien elite bloodlines have usurped mankind since WWII.³²³ The author has no evidence of either, and will keep his private

³¹⁵ It appears more likely that the Earth manufactures the oil, as a form of ‘cholesterol’ for the body of Gaia. There are coal remnants from the megatsunami floods along the sides of Appalachia and the Rockies. Were these errata modified by time, or electricity? Probably time and pressure. However, some sites of obvious electrification, such as the Red River Gorge, KY and its harmonic, the Big South Fork along the same ley line, have rich coal and natural gas deposits, as well. If the coal was made through transmutation, then we can expect massive reserves of so-called “fossil” fuels deeper within the Earth. All the more reason for the author’s proposed deep mining paradigm shift.

³¹⁶ “The thermo-dynamic process is wasteful and barbarous, especially when burning coal, the mining of which, despite modern improvements, still involves dangers to the unfortunate who are condemned to toil deep in the bowels of the earth.” (sic) (Tesla, “Our Future Motive Power”, *Everyday Science and Mechanics*, December **1931**)

Ninety (90) years ago!! <https://racingnelliebly.com/weirdscience/nikola-tesla-papers-envisioned-renewable-energy/>

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC pp. 124

³¹⁸ Climate Change has nothing to do with CO₂

³¹⁹

<https://townhall.com/tipsheet/katiepavlich/2021/08/11/after-canceling-the-keystone-pipeline-biden-begs-opec-for-more-oil-n2593981>

³²⁰ <https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2021/aug/11/joe-biden-asks-opec-oil-output-while-limiting-us-e/>

³²¹ <https://ncadv.org/blog/posts/domestic-violence-and-the-lgbtq-community>

³²² <https://www.nbcnews.com/think/opinion/afghanistan-war-neocons-george-w-bush-would-you-know-1277267>

Of course it isn’t... they only loved the war in Iraq.

³²³ https://www.academia.edu/49955630/Responding_to_the_Cosmic_Hoax

speculation out of this. But mankind has always demonstrated a banal, greedy, selfish, and psychotic behavior for war over trivialities³²⁴ and for lust of resources³²⁵, since ancient times.

Such a lustful form of war, not following the various rules of righteous and just wars (see footnotes) will undoubtedly cause the other powers of the “Big G” (Universal) system to respond. Either your consciousness knows, or the entire Consciousness knows, be it God or Gaia³²⁶, or some amalgamation which Man has termed “Heaven.” Heaven-aether has long been hypothesized and even worshiped, prayed to, etc. for the fortunes of material and good life. As shown in the footnote, the Hebrews saw the Promised Land (which they raped, pillaged, and stole) as a promise from God to build Zion. To this day, this mentality runs Israel, and the Middle East. What’s ironic is there isn’t any oil in Israel itself! Does this stop the hatred of the descendents of Hyksos/Amalekites (sons of Ishmael?) from being directed towards Jews? No, it does not. Because the control of banking cartels continues, and the Power of Numbers remains with the high IQ Jews and set against those coming from war torn and desertified regions like Iraq, Arabia, Egypt, Libya, southern and eastern Persia, Afghanistan, etc. Islam does well in such places, but such places do not have much. Not right now at least.

But can the consciousness of others and self stomach unjust war? Can the next generation, always more liberal than the last, stomach digital images and videos of children blown to smithereens? Probably not. And this modern Industrial Cabal is not able to leverage the ra-ra-hoorahs of “we’re off to fight the Nazis” much longer. Captain America is now retired. He defeated the Red Skull, and the Ironman died. Thor is fat and went to space. The populace is in a different mode of thinking after 16-20 years of War on Terror, and yet the drumbeat of war beats on. And on. And on. China beats it, and the call is there³²⁷. Can patriots summon anything? The author has no idea.

³²⁴ Helen of Troy type situations have been used many times. Consider the Cherokee myths, and their sole entry into why they had to wipe out the Nicotani (Ft. Ancient/Welsh Indians): *“The Nicotani were a mystical, religious body, of whom the people stood in great awe, and seem to have been somewhat like the Brahmins of India. By what means they attained their ascendancy, or how long it was maintained, can never be ascertained. Their extinction by massacre is nearly all that can be discovered concerning them. They became haughty, insolent, overbearing, and licentious to an intolerable degree. Relying on their hereditary privileges and the strange awe which they inspired, they did not hesitate by fraud or violence to rend asunder the tender relations of husband and wife when a beautiful woman excited their passions. The people long brooded in silence over the oppressions and outrages of this high caste, whom they deeply hated but greatly feared. At length a daring young man, a member of an influential family, organized a conspiracy among the people for the massacre of the priesthood. **The immediate provocation was the abduction of the wife of the young leader of the conspiracy. His wife was remarkable for her beauty, and was forcibly abducted and violated by one of the Nicotani while he was absent on the chase. On his return he found no difficulty in exciting in others the resentment which he himself experienced.** So many had suffered in the same way, so many feared that they might be made to suffer, that nothing was wanted but a leader. A leader appearing in the person of the young brave whom we have named, the people rose under his direction and killed every Nicotani, young and old. Thus perished a hereditary secret society, since which time no hereditary privileges have been tolerated among the Cherokees.”*

<https://www.gutenberg.org/files/45634/45634-h/45634-h.htm#s108>

³²⁵ **Numbers 13:23-30** *“23 When they reached the Valley of Eshkol, they cut off a branch bearing a single cluster of grapes. Two of them carried it on a pole between them, along with some pomegranates and figs. 24 That place was called the Valley of Eshkol because of the cluster of grapes the Israelites cut off there. 25 At the end of forty days they returned from exploring the land. 26 They came back to Moses and Aaron and the whole Israelite community at Kadesh in the Desert of Paran. There they reported to them and to the whole assembly and showed them the fruit of the land. 27 They gave Moses this account: **“We went into the land to which you sent us, and it does flow with milk and honey! Here is its fruit. 28 But the people who live there are powerful, and the cities are fortified and very large. We even saw descendants of Anak there. 29 The Amalekites live in the Negev; the Hittites, Jebusites and Amorites live in the hill country; and the Canaanites live near the sea and along the Jordan.”** 30 Then Caleb silenced the people before Moses and said, **“We should go up and take possession of the land, for we can certainly do it.”**”*

So much for “Thou Shalt Not Steal.”

³²⁶ <https://courses.seas.harvard.edu/climate/eli/Courses/EPS281r/Sources/Gaia/Gaia-hypothesis-wikipedia.pdf>

³²⁷ Or else shall the Fourth Reich and China’s new holocaust go unavenged?

But that won't stop the anti-MIMS. That's the key to it. There are rules to Yin and Yang polarities³²⁸. When true yin and yang fail, because the rules are not understood or ignored, toxic or false yin and yang emerge. The original supportive rules, such as mutual control, or mutual opposition, or mutual/infinite divisibility become the harbingers of death and the "horsemen of the Apocalypse."

Consider a marriage. What starts as mutual support can turn to mutual hatred. Without the deft knowledge of the Law of Polarity, the Law of Relativity sitting opposite to it³²⁹ can generate such toxic situations that we see violence unbelievable, among domesticated non-soldiers! Beheadings, kidnappings, rape, arson, and murder.³³⁰ True horrors³³¹ for children and families, and destruction of what originally started as a Union of Bliss. How? It is the polarity sub rules within that domain of the *P* power, being ignored, and then the nonlinear dynamics *flipping or inverting*³³² the situation, unexpectedly, and quickly. Then honors are broken, reputations insulted, and redress or even vengeance is sought.

This can happen on a much larger scale. And when false yin begins to consume all, in a mad bid to fulfill material needs of a person or populace (a Borg³³³ or evil gestalt), then the natural expectation is a response. Not all people or societies can remain patient and spiritual, to await righteous anger and move into motion as America did in 1941 or Britain in 1939. More often, false yang (and its attendant hypermasculinity³³⁴) react, and explosively.

If China convinces its population they are oppressed by the west and not the CCP, and the Allies are the bourgeoisie oppressors *they expected*, then even the "Declaration of Independence," "Bill of Rights," "Geneva Conventions," and freedom itself can become the patent enemy of the People. This is, of course, absurd. But as George Orwell wrote in 1984, the three nations or our three-body problem is not about Truth.

- ❖ "Doublethink means the power of holding two contradictory beliefs in one's mind simultaneously, and accepting both of them."
- ❖ "If you want a picture of the future, imagine a boot stamping on a human face—forever."
- ❖ "War is peace. Freedom is slavery. Ignorance is strength."
- ❖ "Who controls the past controls the future. Who controls the present controls the past."
- ❖ "Until they become conscious they will never rebel, and until after they have rebelled they cannot become conscious."

It is about Control.

This is how we head into the space race: no longer as International Space Station builders but destroyers of it³³⁵. No longer looking for moonbases to make into spaceports to make it to Jupiter and beyond, but to make them strategic bases³³⁶ to look **down upon** our fellow man³³⁷. Why now? Because that's the state we now occupy that we did not in 1960 when the war machine felt its cockles bursting with aggressive,

³²⁸ See the writings of Liu Yiming, such as "The Book of Balance and Harmony" transl. By T. Cleary

³²⁹ https://www.academia.edu/50804985/Trigram_Law_Bagua_Dharma_Short_document_single_page_reference

³³⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC69uYUqyx-vw4luuX7aHNLQ>

³³¹ <https://www.youtube.com/user/HorrorStories666>

³³² Jueyin; see

<https://classicalchinesemedicine.org/six-conformation-diagnosis-in-context-the-six-cosmic-qi-liu-qi-and-the-six-stages-of-qi-transformation-liu-jing/>

³³³ <https://memory-alpha.fandom.com/wiki/Borg>

³³⁴ https://www.academia.edu/40245389/Boxing_Out_Hyper_Masculinity

³³⁵ <https://futurism.com/nasa-trying-kill-international-space-station>

³³⁶ <https://interestingengineering.com/us-military-plans-to-build-factories-on-the-moon>

³³⁷ <https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/07/us-air-force-cadets-study-idea-space-force-bases-moon>

expansionist, almost religious pro-American zeal. Sure, the filthy seeds of fiat³³⁸, of “social security” lies^{339 340}, of war profiteering and propaganda, and of socialism and communism had been sown all by 1938. But the MIMS that gave them flight was War. Pure, unending, tasteless, nation respectless, sovereignty destroying, globalizing, and feudalistic war. It underscores the alternate “Golden Rule,” and that the only color that matters is “green” (as in money, which increasingly not green or black but invisible³⁴¹). If the GRUNCH of Giants continues, and the war machine “reloads” for a World War III (beyond the New Cold War and WW3.0), then Einstein’s warning may prove founded,

“I know not with what weapons World War III will be fought, but World War IV will be fought with sticks and stones”³⁴²

Conclusion

We have gleaned two hypotheses, and maybe more than any MIMS paper before, laid strong evidence at their feet. In fact, one could say the *batteries* of our *guns* put heft to the idea that the “pen is mightier than the sword.” One may suppose that it is because the ‘pen’ is now connected to the PEMF via the computer (*N* power), and internet, which may itself be conscious (*L* power? One hopes not), that it is far, far mightier than the sword. And yet, it is the sword - thunderbolt inspired - for which we are here to discuss these hypotheses:

Figure 29 - Battleship Gun Batteries ([gif](#)); credit: World of Warships

- ★ (VII) - Government is the worst MIMS ever created
- ★ (VIII) - War is our first identified anti-MIMS and characterized by robbing material richness, and therefore life, rather than aiding it.³⁴³
 - Therefore the Membranous Interface can indeed have a form of undesired “reverse osmosis”

³³⁸ “The Creature from Jekyll Island,” G. Griffin, 1994

³³⁹

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/timworstall/2017/04/04/sure-social-securitys-a-ponzi-scheme-but-is-it-a-sustainable-one-or-not/?sh=4e380393ab61>

³⁴⁰ <https://elderlawaustin.com/social-security-ponzi-scheme/>

³⁴¹ If invisible, can the spongy counterspace absorb it back into the *A* power? Perhaps another MIMS finance short paper?

³⁴² Actually we do not know if he said this or not. That’s how bad truthiness has become.

<https://www.snopes.com/fact-check/einstein-world-war-iv-sticks-stones/>

³⁴³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F1IDXlyR-2M>

Where to go from here with the mimsical analysis is not clear. The author's strategy series is already potentially 2.7.1, ect. Currently in edit is the "Winning the New Cold War" paper, which is a mimsical product. Many of the citations in this paper (such as ally lists) relate to this product. But the author would like to emphasize that the mimsical product within it, the "Solution Sets"³⁴⁴ emphasize 80% or so positive activities, and yet 20% or so attacking. The author is not shy about the preparedness, or the need for it. The Chinese (unironically) said this long ago, "animals have their claws, and mankind has his weapons." So we see the logical conclusion as to why war will "always exist." Yet the author cautions the reader that the Laws of Polarity and Relativity are very slippery and difficult to grasp. What appears one way one day may appear different the next. What seems right and wrong may shift beneath the feet.

It is in times when an oppressive "mental bloodline" such as the Ruling Class/Caste pushes the peasantry towards something "we must do" that the author suspects this is when questions are most needed. Especially when it comes to suddenly voting against freedom and liberties, as happened post 9/11. The motion towards tyranny and war should always, always, always be questioned. Violence should be avoided in interpersonal space, as well as extrapersonal (if possible.) Romans 12:18 says, "If it be possible, as much as lieth in you, live peaceably with all men." Whether you look at this as "well a Roman would know" or as a Judeo-Christian, it is of course, *good common sense wisdom* because it is not always possible. Yet, where it is, "all men" includes those who are evil and wicked (such as pedophiles/elite/war criminals), or entire parties such as ISIL or the CCP. You cannot keep peace with evil forever, but you can most of the time.

Where the philosophy goes from here will be a decidedly positive switchback as well as a deepening of martiality. However, the author cautions the readers to look for other anti-MIMS (such as Wokeism, Critical Theory, Racial Supremacy doctrines, abortion, ... so Socialism and Cultural Marxism in general, etc.) in all domains, like science, medicine, law, business, etc. Look for it and call it out. Take this philosophy and apply it with rigor in all directions.

Because this was such a difficult topic, especially post Afghanistan, the author offers the words of the Desiderata,

"GO PLACIDLY amid the noise and the haste, and remember what peace there may be in silence. As far as possible, without surrender, be on good terms with all persons. ... Avoid loud and aggressive persons; they are vexatious to the spirit. If you compare yourself with others, you may become vain or bitter, for always there will be greater and lesser persons than yourself. ... Exercise caution in your business affairs, for the world is full of trickery. But let this not blind you to what virtue there is; many persons strive for high ideals, and everywhere life is full of heroism. ... Nurture strength of spirit to shield you in sudden misfortune. But do not distress yourself with dark imaginings. ... Beyond a wholesome discipline, be gentle with yourself. You are a child of the universe no less than the trees and the stars; you have a right to be here. ... Therefore be at peace with God, whatever you conceive Him to be. And whatever your labors and aspirations, in the noisy confusion of life, keep peace in your soul. With all its sham, drudgery and broken dreams, it is still a beautiful world. Be cheerful. Strive to be happy." ~M. Ehrmann³⁴⁵, 1927³⁴⁶ (selections)

³⁴⁴ Ibid. pp. 18

³⁴⁵ <https://www.desiderata.com/desiderata.html>

³⁴⁶ The last year of the Great Enlightenment, and birth of the two cosmologies. Sadly, Einstein's rock star status caused mankind to sway into the wrong one. How unique that this poem was birthed then.

References

1. "Shang Di Heaven and Dao," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao
2. "Caer Melyn (Camelot) -Cosmic Hillfort of the King The Yellow Hill (fort) as a Cosmic Hill or mountain motif and symbol of a King's authority," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority
3. "Uchell, the High Lord, and Shang Di," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di
4. "On the Membranous Interface of the Material and the Spiritual (from an EPEMC perspective) & Dual/Double Layer Economics... a proposed test of EPEMC's 'metallic' properties: tensile strength, malleability, durability," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability
5. "Avatar," Imsdb.com., J. Cameron, <https://imsdb.com/scripts/Avatar.html>
6. Chinese Etymology, "<https://hanziyuan.net/#home>
7. "Deities & Immortals," China.org.cn., <http://www.china.org.cn/english/daodejingforum/208124.htm>
8. "Addendum 2: Megafauna Extinction Events Update to the Thunderbolt Extinction Model; the Surprising truth of the Younger Dryas Event that Changes Everything," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50939161/Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything
9. "Agora- Ancient Greek Meeting Place, Encyclopedia Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/agora>
10. "To the Gates of Fengtu," L.B. Nickless, 2017
11. "Chinese Etymology," <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E5%B0%86> & <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E8%BB%8D>
12. "Divine right of kings political doctrine," Encyclopedia Britannica, "The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica," <https://www.britannica.com/topic/divine-right-of-kings>
13. "Rectification of names," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rectification_of_names
14. "King Tut's Sisters Took the Throne Before He Did, Controversial Claim Says," Live Science, L. Geggel, 2019, <https://www.livescience.com/65433-king-tut-sisters-pharaoh.html>
15. "Alalu: Anatolian God," Encyclopedia Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Alalu>
16. "The Melammu Project: The Heritage of Mesopotamia and the Ancient Near East," melammu-project, http://melammu-project.eu/database/gen_html/a0001230.html
17. "The Castrated Gods and their Castration Cults: Revenge, Punishment, and Spiritual Supremacy," Digital Commons@ CHS (California Institute of Integral Studies,) J. Wade, 2019, <https://digitalcommons.ciis.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1011&context=advance-archive>
18. "Examples of castration myths besides Ouranos," Stack Exchange/Mythology and Folklore, 2019, <https://mythology.stackexchange.com/questions/6114/examples-of-castration-myths-besides-ouranos>
19. "Zeus' Lovers: Myths," greekmythology.com., https://www.greekmythology.com/Myths/The_Myths/Zeus%27s_Lovers/zeus%27s_lovers.html
20. "Hera," World History Encyclopedia, M. Cartwright, 2012, <https://www.worldhistory.org/Hera/>
21. Epic of Gilgamesh: Mesopotamian literature, Encyclopedia Britannica, "The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica," <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Epic-of-Gilgamesh>

22. "Thor and the Midgard Serpent," Pitt.edu., D. L. Ashliman 1997, <https://sites.pitt.edu/~dash/thorserpent.html>
23. "Akhenaten and Monotheism," USU 1320: History and Civilization Section 10, Damen, 2019, <http://www.usu.edu/markdamen/1320Hist&Civ/chapters/10AKHEN.htm>
24. "Sun Tzu's The Art of War, Illustrated (Chapter 2: Waging War), Forbes, J.Hagy, 2013, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jessicahagy/2013/10/03/sun-tzus-the-art-of-war-illustrated-chapter-2/?sh=5ed15a6c4e60>
25. "The 5 Worst Roman Emperors," HH/Historyhit.com., C. Ricketts, 2021, <https://www.historyhit.com/worst-roman-emperors/>
26. 3500 BCE-600 BCE "On the Origins of Religions," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions
27. "Divine Kingship in Ancient China," Numen Volume 4, JSTOR, D.H. Smith, 1957, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3269343>
28. "Three Sovereigns and Five Emperors," New World Encyclopedia, New World Encyclopedia contributors, 2008, https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/p/index.php?title=Special:CiteThisPage&page=Three_Sovereigns_and_Five_Empereors&id=706400
29. "The Motif of Legendary Emperors Yao and Shun in Ancient Chinese Literature," ResearchGate/ Peter Lang Editors, D. Rogacz, 2017, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320372005_The_Motif_of_Legendary_Empereors_Yao_and_Shun_in_Ancient_Chinese_Literature
30. "Yao and Shun in the Cantos: Chinese Emperors Placed in the Context of Frazer's 'The Golden Bough.' Paideuma: Modern and Contemporary Poetry and Poetics Volume 17/JSTOR, E. Bruce, 1988, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24724948>
31. "Yu the Great," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yu_the_Great
32. "Emperor Yao," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emperor_Yao
33. "Enki & The World Order," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2020, https://www.academia.edu/51008599/Enki_and_The_World_Order
34. "Hopewellian Octagons Proof that the Allegewi Astronomers could see Jupiter up close; Analysis of the Octagon formations of Chillicothe and Newark Earthworks," ResearchGate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks
35. "The Notions of God in the Ancient Chinese Religion," Numen, Volume 16/JSTOR, J. Shih, 1969, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3269759>
36. "Emperor Shun," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emperor_Shun
37. "Ancient Egyptian quarries– an illustrated overview," Geological Survey of Norway Special Publication, J. Harrell and P. Storemyr, https://www.ngu.no/upload/Publikasjoner/Special%20publication/SP12_s7-50.pdf
38. "Ancient Egyptian Architecture," World History Encyclopedia J. Mark, 2016, https://www.worldhistory.org/Egyptian_Architecture/
39. "How much would it cost to build the Great Pyramid today?" NBC News: Science, N. Wolchover, 2012, <https://www.nbcnews.com/id/wbna46485163>
40. "Are Olmec Scripts Chinese? A Study on the Olmec Iconographic Symbols and Mesoamerican Writing," Sino-platonic.org., Z. He, 2017, http://sino-platonic.org/complete/spp273_olmec_chinese_writing.pdf
41. "Explaining Aztec Human Sacrifice," The Department of Studies in Religion , University of Queensland St Lucia, Australia, R. Kerkhove Thesis, 1994, http://www.famsi.org/research/thesis_dissertations/KerkhoveR_thesis.pdf
42. "Human Sacrifice at Tenochtitlan," Comparative Studies in Society and History, Vol.26/JSTOR, J. Ingham, 1984, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/178547>
43. "The Pawnee Mythology 1906," American tribes.com., G.A. Dorsey, 2017, <https://amertribes.proboards.com/thread/2570/dorsey-editor-pawnee-mythology-1906>

44. "Returning God or Blood Sacrifice: What were Moctezuma's Intentions Towards Cortes?" A Thesis presented to the Faculty of the Graduate School at the University of Missouri-Columbia, L. Kile, 2011, <https://mospace.umsystem.edu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10355/11179/research.pdf?sequence=3>
45. "Who Answered the Shang Diviner?: The Nature of Shang Divination" Journal of Confucian Philosophy and Culture, Y. Back, 2017, https://www.academia.edu/33852373/Who_Answered_the_Shang_Diviner_The_Nature_of_Shang_Divination
46. "Axioms of Influence, Affluence, and Access," Sf. R. Careaga, 2020
47. "Kublai Khan: Emperor of Yuan dynasty," Britannica, C. Bawden, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Kublai-Khan>
48. "Zeus VS. Cronus," Myths and Legends, <http://myths.e2bn.org/mythsandlegends/userstory20415-zeus-vs-cronus.html>
49. "14 Times The Greek Gods Shapeshifted To Rape Mortals," The Collector/thecollector.com., A.Chaliakopoulos, 2021, <https://www.thecollector.com/greek-mythology-rape-transformation/>
50. "'Structure of the Asteroid Belt for Small Members," Celestial Mechanics & Dynamical Astronomy, Volume 57, T. Nakamura, 1993, <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1993CeMDA..57...57N>
51. "The Cause of Jupiter's Glowing 'Northern Lights' is Finally Revealed," Inverse.com., 2021, <https://www.inverse.com/science/juno-jupiter-aurora-discovery>
52. "Swastika," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swastika>
53. "Enuma Elish The Epic of Creation," The Seven Tablets of Creation, L.W. King, 1902, <https://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm>
54. "The Mesopotamian Pantheon," World History, J.J. Mark, 2011, <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/221/the-mesopotamian-pantheon/>
55. "Appendix: Chart of Olympian Gods and their Akkadian Counterparts," onlinelibrary.wiley.com. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/9781444308549.app1>
56. "Titan," World History, M. Cartwright, 2013, <https://www.worldhistory.org/Titan/>
57. "late Middle English: from Old French benivolent, from Latin bene volent- 'well wishing', from bene 'well' + velle 'to wish'" (Oxford Languages). Isn't it curious how similar that word is to "violence"? "Middle English: via Old French from Latin violentia, from violent- 'vehement, violent'" ???
58. "MIMS 2.1.1-2 : Aether, Business & Analytics; With a short reflection upon the philosophies of Ayn Rand and the concepts of Fortune as it relates to the Aether," Academia, Sf. R.Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether
59. "NY's New Gov. Announces That Cuomo's Nursing Home Scandal Was Way Worse Than Earlier Reported," Patriot Alerts.com., 2021, <https://patriotalerts.com/2021/08/nys-new-gov-announces-that-cuomos-nursing-home-scandal-was-way-worse-than-earlier-reported/>
60. "Plato Meets the Meteorite: Solon, Egypt and Atlantis," Strange History.net. 2014, <http://www.strangehistory.net/2014/02/22/plato-meets-the-meteorite-solon-egypt-and-atlantis/>
61. The Atrahasis Text:"Myths from Mesopotamia," <https://geha.paginas.ufsc.br/files/2017/04/Atrahasis.pdf>
62. "Plasma Petroglyphs (Plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction
63. "ATHENA. Athena, the Greek goddess of wisdom, war, the arts, industry, justice and skill Daughter of Zeus and Metis Athena, the Greek goddess of.," Slide player.com., P Pickles, <https://slideplayer.com/slide/4110893/>
64. "The tail of Venus: When the solar wind nearly breaks off, our neighbour's ionosphere expands into space," Max Planck Gesellschaft, Y. Wei et al., 2013, https://www.mpg.de/6882886/Schweif_der_Venus
65. "Comparative plasma tails of Venus and comets," Harvard.edu., H. Perezdetejada, 1987, <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1987sici.symp...38P/abstract>

-
66. "Sumo: Ancient Ritual to the Thunder God," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God
 67. "Starf*cker," Ev Cochrane, 2010 <http://cista.net/tomes//Electric%20Universe/Ev%20Cochrane/Starfucker.pdf>
 68. "The Saturn Myth," D. Talbott, 1980
 69. "Montezuma's revenge: Cannibalism in the age of The Conquistadors," Independent, D. Osborne, 2011, <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/americas/montezuma-s-revenge-cannibalism-in-the-age-of-the-conquistadors-413272.html>
 70. "The Death of Quetzalcōātl," Anales de Cuauhtitlan (Codex Chimalpopoca, sections 5 to 8), <https://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>
 71. "Battle of Tenochtitlán: Mexican history (1521,)" Britannica Encyclopedia, M. Hudson, <https://www.britannica.com/event/Battle-of-Tenochtitlan>
 72. "Ancient Maya sacrificed boys not virgin girls: study," Reuters Science and Space, By Reuters Staff, 2008, <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-mexico-sacrifice/ancient-maya-sacrificed-boys-not-virgin-girls-study-idUSWRI32680820080123>
 73. "Conquistadors sacrificed and eaten by Aztec-era people, archaeologists say. The Guardian, A. Yuhas, 2015, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2015/oct/10/conquistadors-sacrificed-eaten-aztec-acolhuas>
 74. "To the Gates of Fengtu," L.B. Nickless, 2015
 75. "Chasing Dragons: the True History of the Piasa," M. Nickless, 2012
 76. "500 years ago, China destroyed its world-dominating navy because its political elite was afraid of free trade," Insider, J. Edwards, 2017, <https://www.businessinsider.com/china-zhenge-he-treasure-fleet-elite-free-trade-2017-2>
 77. "How did the gold of the new world cause the Spanish Empire to collapse?" Stack Exchange, 2013, <https://history.stackexchange.com/questions/9060/how-did-the-gold-of-the-new-world-cause-the-spanish-empire-to-collapse>
 78. "British Empire Timeline 1588 ," Encyclopedia Britannica, By The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com/summary/British-Empire-Timeline>
 79. "How did the defeat of the Spanish Armada (1588) change England?," Daily History.com., [https://dailyhistory.org/How_did_the_defeat_of_the_Spanish_Armada_\(1588\)_change_England%3F](https://dailyhistory.org/How_did_the_defeat_of_the_Spanish_Armada_(1588)_change_England%3F)
 80. "GRUNCH of Giants," B. Fuller, 1983
 81. "In Easter Island DNA, Evidence of Genetic Loneliness," The New York Times: Science, 2017, <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/10/12/science/easter-island-dna-south-america.html>
 82. "Review: The Making of Cook's Death," The Journal of Pacific History/ JSTOR, K. R. Howe, 1996, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25169289>
 83. "European Americans and Native Americans View Each Other, 1700-1775," National Humanities Center, <http://nationalhumanitiescenter.org/pds/becomingamer/peoples/text3/indianscolonists.pdf>
 84. "Palace of Versailles: Facts & History," Live Science, O. Jarus, 2017, <https://www.livescience.com/38903-palace-of-versailles-facts-history.html>
 85. " Key Concepts in Chinese Thought and Culture," https://www.chinesethought.cn/EN/shuyu_show.aspx?shuyu_id=4131
 86. "China's Artificial Sun Just Smashed a Fusion World Record," Popular Mechanics, C. Delbert, 2021, <https://www.popularmechanics.com/science/energy/a36630528/china-artificial-sun-breaks-fusion-world-record/>
 87. "Collector's Edge Minerals Purchases The World's Largest Float Copper," Collector's Edge Minerals/ collectors edge.com., <https://collectorsedge.com/news-updates/collectors-edge-minerals-purchases-the-worlds-largest-float-copper/>
 88. "China wants to be a leading space power by 2045—and it's getting there fast," Fortune.com., E. Barrett, 2021, <https://fortune.com/2021/05/30/china-space-race-rocket-landing-mars-us/>
 89. "JUST IN: Studies Shed Light on Chinese Directed Energy Efforts," National Defense Magazine, M. Mayfield, 2021, <https://www.nationaldefensemagazine.org/articles/2021/4/8/study-sheds-light-on-chinese-directed-energy-program>

90. "This Day in History: May 19,1967 Soviets ratify treaty banning nuclear weapons from outer space," History.com., By History Editors, 2009, <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/soviets-ratify-treaty-banning-nuclear-weapons-from-outer-space>
91. "Action/Reaction: U.S. Space Weaponization and China: Arms Control Today," Arms Control Association/ armscontrol.org., H. Zhang, 2005, <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2005-12/features/actionreaction-us-space-weaponization-china>
92. "Reconsidering the Rules of Space: Chapter 2: Chinese Perspectives on Space Weapons," American Academy of Arts and Sciences, P. Podvig and H. Zhang, <https://www.amacad.org/publication/russian-and-chinese-responses-us-military-plans-space/section/4>
93. "Rethinking Nuclear Arms Control," The Washington Quarterly, R. Gottemoeller, 2020, https://cgsr.llnl.gov/content/assets/docs/Gottemoeller_TWQ_43-3.pdf
94. "History of Imperial Mausoleum in China," DeepLogic Publisher, Z. Dao, <https://books.google.com/books?id=YbKLDwAAQBAJ>
95. "Did humans domesticate themselves?" Science Daily, Universidad de Barcelona, 2018, <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/02/180215110041.htm>
96. "The Bohemian Grove: Facts & Fiction," M. Dice, 2015
97. "Bohemian Grove," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bohemian_Grove
98. Hou Yi (后羿), Mythopedia.com., M. Hamilton, <https://mythopedia.com/chinese-mythology/gods/hou-yi/>
99. "The Government Says We Should Use Nukes to Deflect Asteroids," Popular Mechanics, C. Delbert, 2021, <https://www.popularmechanics.com/space/a36122690/government-tests-using-nuclear-weapons-to-deflect-asteroids/>
100. "Trishula," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trishula>
101. "10 Legendary Weapons in Norse Mythology, Norse Mythology Blog, <https://blog.vkngjewelry.com/en/weapons-norse-mythology/>
102. "Ragnarök," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ragnar%C3%B6k>
103. "Electric Discharge Caused the Formation of Upheaval Dome," R. Hawthorne Jr., 2019 https://becomingborealis.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Electric-Discharge-Caused-the-Formation-of-Upheaval-Dome_002.pdf
104. "Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge
105. "Evidence for an intense solar outburst in prehistory," IOP Publishing, A L Peratt1 and W F Yao, 2008, https://plasmauniverse.info/downloads-petros/Peratt&YaoAurora-PrehistoryPhys-Scr-T131_2008c.pdf
106. "Vajra," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vajra>
107. "Vitrified fort," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vitrified_fort
108. "Huracan," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Huracan>
109. "Enki & The World Order," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2020, https://www.academia.edu/51008599/Enki_and_The_World_Order
110. "The Legend of Devils Tower," indiancountrytoday.com., By ICT Staff, 2017, <https://indiancountrytoday.com/archive/the-legend-of-devils-tower>
111. "Where Does the Concept of a "Grim Reaper" Come From?," Encyclopedia Britannica, A. McKenna, <https://www.britannica.com/story/where-does-the-concept-of-a-grim-reaper-come-from>
112. "Nuclear Program Spending (Responses)," Sf. R. Careaga, https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1On7Pht_01P3bl0FqR2InohoMnCcuaam2QWelqOC_p55c/edit#gid=1363061005
113. "The Water in Saturn's Rings and Satellites is Like That on Earth Except for Saturn's Moon Phoebe, Which is Out of This World," Planetary Science Institute/ psi.edu., 2018, <https://www.psi.edu/news/phoebewater>
114. "Laser-guided energetic discharges over large air gaps by electric-field enhanced plasma filaments, Scientific Reports/Nature.com., F. Théberge et al., 2017, <https://www.nature.com/articles/srep40063>
115. "Enough is Enough: Global Nuclear Weapons Spending 2019," The International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons/ICANW.org., 2020, https://www.icanw.org/report_73_billion_nuclear_weapons_spending_2020

-
116. "China: Nuclear," Nuclear Threat Initiative/nti.org., 2015, <https://www.nti.org/learn/countries/china/nuclear/>
 117. "Russian Military Budget," nuke.fas.org., 2000, <https://nuke.fas.org/guide/russia/agency/mo-budget.htm>
 118. "Russia: Nuclear," Nuclear Threat Initiative/nti.org., 2018, <https://www.nti.org/learn/countries/russia/nuclear/>
 119. "The Hidden Costs of Our Nuclear Arsenal," Brookings Institution, S. I. Schwartz, 1998, <https://www.brookings.edu/the-hidden-costs-of-our-nuclear-arsenal-overview-of-project-findings/>
 120. "Book- Atomic Audit: The Costs and Consequences of U.S. Nuclear Weapons Since 1940," S. I. Schwartz, 1998, <https://www.brookings.edu/book/atomic-audit/>
 121. "Recent Analysis on Nuclear Weapons Spending," Center for Arms Control and Non-Proliferation/ arms control center.org., 2021, <https://armscontrolcenter.org/issues/security-spending/nuclear-weapons-spending/>
 122. "What Does China Really Spend on its Military?" Center for Strategic and International Studies: China Power Project, 2021, <https://chinapower.csis.org/military-spending/>
 123. "Average Household Cost of Food," valuepenguin.com., S. Price, <https://www.valuepenguin.com/how-much-we-spend-food>
 124. "Our World in Data," <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/share-of-consumer-expenditure-spent-on-food-vs-gdp-per-capita?tab=table>
 125. Also called the Hammered Bracelet
 126. "French Revolution: Tnew New Regime," Encyclopedia Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com/event/French-Revolution/The-new-regime>
 127. "Early China: Signs, Clues, and Traces: Anticipation In Ancient Chinese Political and Military Texts," Cambridge University Press, A. Galvany, 2015, <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/early-china/article/abs/signs-clues-and-traces-anticipation-in-ancient-chinese-political-and-military-texts/BFA26131161A6FB1FA0F9551BD1E4F48>
 128. "The Saturn Myth," D. Talbott, https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/118Tbu6mdDBTRaYJyBtLwMSkN4-Usz02j_tR_pKx6uos/edit#gid=0
 129. "Chinese Natural Philosophæ (Physics) inExtended-Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC
 130. "Ancient Origins of Taijiquan Do plasmaglyphics belie a more ancient origin of the internal martial art of Taijiquan? An EPEMC Analysis," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/39776252/Ancient_Origins_of_Taijiquan_Do_plasmaglyphics_belie_a_more_ancient_origin_of_the_internal_martial_art_of_Taijiquan_An_EPEMC_Analysis
 131. "Loki," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Loki>
 132. "Arthur: First King of Britain," Wilson & Blackett
 133. "The King Arthur Conspiracy," Wilson & Blackett
 134. King Arthur's Voyage to the Otherworld," R. MacCann, 2016
 135. "The Quest for the Holy Grail," <https://www.bl.uk/onlinegallery/features/mythical/grail.html>
 136. "Egyptian Origin of The Word Christ," Honorable W. Brewer, <https://opensiuc.lib.siu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2226&context=ocj>
 137. "The Contendings of Horus and Seth," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Contendings_of_Horus_and_Seth
 138. "Ancient Egypt," History/History.com., By History.com Editors, 2009, <https://www.history.com/topics/ancient-history/ancient-egypt>
 139. "The Holy Kingdom," A. Gilbert, 1998
 140. "Man stabs brother in fight over TV remote," Fox 5, San Diego, B. Hart, 2015, <https://fox5sandiego.com/news/man-stabs-brother-after-fighting-over-tv-remote/>
 141. "16-year-old boy fatally stabs older brother after argument over TV remote," meaww.com., A. Pai, 2018, <https://meaww.com/16-year-old-boy-arrested-fatal-stabbing-older-brother-argument-tv-remote-control>
 142. "The Opium of the Intellectuals," W. W. Norton & Company, Inc., R. Aron, Translated by T. Kilmartin, 1962, https://monoskop.org/images/7/73/Aron_Raymond_The_Opium_of_the_Intellectuals.pdf
 143. "Alphabet agencies," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alphabet_agencies

144. "How colonial railroads defined Africa's economic geography," Voxeu.org., R. Jedwab, E. Kerby & A. Moradi, 2017, <https://voxeu.org/article/how-colonial-railroads-defined-africa-s-economic-geography>
145. "Guns, Germs, and Steel," J. Diamond, 1997
146. "Rwanda: How the genocide happened," BBC News: Africa, 2011, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-13431486>
147. "Genocide in Darfur," Holocaust Museum Houston, <https://hnh.org/library/research/genocide-in-darfur-guide/>
148. "'But I'm not racist': Black Panther, Wakanda, The Spear, The Shield, & 'The Anatomy of Trust'." Medium.com L. E. Colston II, 2018, <https://medium.com/@Mr.Write/but-im-not-racist-wakanda-the-spear-the-shield-the-anatomy-of-trust-f513f736110d>
149. "15 reasons why Black Panther is a nationalist, xenophobic, colonial and racist movie, 20 JAAR" J. Slaats, 2018, <https://kifkif.be/cnt/artikel/15-reasons-why-black-panther-nationalist-xenophobic-colonial-and-racist-movie-6036>
150. "Why Foreign Aid Is Hurting Africa," The Wall Street Journal, D. Moyo, 2009, <https://www.wsj.com/articles/SB123758895999200083>
151. "Humanitarian Assistance and Conflict in Africa," United States Institute of Peace, D. R. Smock, 1996, <https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/pwks6.pdf>
152. "Etymology of the word: Corporation, <https://freedom-school.com/history/the-corporation.pdf>
153. "U.S. Code collection," web archive.org., http://web.archive.org/web/20060708190425/http://assembler.law.cornell.edu/uscode/html/uscode28/usc_sec_28_00003002----000-.html
154. "List of armed conflicts involving the United States," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_armed_conflicts_involving_the_United_States
155. "American Indian Wars," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/American_Indian_Wars
156. "Remembering Catarino Garza's 1891 Revolution: An Aborted Border Insurrection," Mexican Studies/Vol. 12, No. 2/JSTOR, E. Young, 1996, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1051845>
157. "Costs of Major US Wars Congressional Research Service Report for Congress (RS22926)," Naval History and Heritage Command, S. Daggett, 2008, <https://www.history.navy.mil/research/library/online-reading-room/title-list-alphabetically/c/costs-major-us-wars.html>
158. "What were the 13 most expensive wars in U.S. history?" USA Today, J. Harrington & G. Suneson, 2019, <https://www.usatoday.com/story/money/2019/06/13/cost-of-war-13-most-expensive-wars-in-us-history/39556983/>
159. "Coal Wars," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coal_Wars
160. "50 Years Later: Learning From The Bay Of Pigs," NPR: All Things Considered, By NPR Staff, 2011, <https://www.npr.org/2011/04/17/135444482/50-years-later-learning-from-the-bay-of-pigs>
161. "Libya War Costs for US: \$ 896 million so far," The Washington Post, J. Ukman, 2011, https://www.washingtonpost.com/blogs/checkpoint-washington/post/libya-war-costs-for-us-896-million-so-far/2011/08/23/gIQA5KpYJ_blog.html
162. "CNN Fact Check: Comparing costs of Iraq, Libya missions," CNN: Politics, By CNn Wire Staff, 2012, <https://www.cnn.com/2012/10/23/politics/fact-check-libya-cost/index.html>
163. "Political Airpower, Part I: Say No to the No-Fly Zone," Warontherocks.com., M. Benitez & M. Pietrucha, 2016, <https://warontherocks.com/2016/10/political-airpower-part-i-say-no-to-the-no-fly-zone/>
164. "The true cost of the 20-year war in Afghanistan, in 5 charts," Fortune.com., N. Goodkind & N. Rapp, 2021, <https://fortune.com/2021/08/18/cost-of-afghanistan-war-time-casualties-deaths-money/>
165. "Financial cost of the Iraq War," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Financial_cost_of_the_Iraq_War
166. "Iraq war costs U.S. more than \$2 trillion: study," Reuters, D. Trotta, 2013, <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-iraq-war-anniversary/iraq-war-costs-u-s-more-than-2-trillion-study-idUSBRE92D0PG20130314>
167. "Operation Inherent Resolve Targeted Operations to Defeat ISIS," DOD, <https://dod.defense.gov/OIR/>
168. "Armed Conflict in Syria: Overview and U.S. Response," Congressional Research Service, C. E. Humud & C. M. Blanchard, 2020, <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/mideast/RL33487.pdf>
169. "Too High a Price to Pay: The Cost of Conflict for Syria's children," Relief Web, 2021, <https://reliefweb.int/report/syrian-arab-republic/too-high-price-pay-cost-conflict-syrias-children>

170. "National Security Adviser Jake Sullivan says 'several thousand Americans' are still stuck in Afghanistan," Insider/businessinsider.com., F. Augustin, 2021, <https://www.businessinsider.com/wh-says-thousands-of-americans-are-still-stuck-in-kabul-2021-8>
171. "Death toll rises in Kabul attack as US presses on with evacuations despite fears of more attacks," Associated Press/ WBAL TV (Baltimore) 2021, <https://www.wbalv.com/article/afghanistan-1-500-americans-may-still-await-evacuation/37398140>
172. "170 Years of America's Evolution In One Animated GIF," Smithsonian Magazine, C. Schultz, 2012, <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/170-years-of-americas-evolution-in-one-animated-gif-12784190/>
173. "See the world's foreign military bases from outer space," tni.org., 2007, <https://www.tni.org/es/node/13055>
174. "Locke's Political Philosophy," Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, J. Locke, 2005, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/locke-political>
175. "Liberty or tyranny? Vaccine Passports are coming," TRT World, <https://www.trtworld.com/video/tv-shows/liberty-or-tyranny-vaccine-passports-are-coming/6079776c3b0f87001e8df323>
176. "'Washington public school forces unvaccinated teens to wear ankle monitors' as a condition of playing team sports.," Politifact.com., E. Tian, 2021, <https://www.politifact.com/factchecks/2021/aug/25/facebook-posts/proximity-monitors-wash-school-are-vaccinated-stud/>
177. "COVID-19, culture wars, gun violence show America's irrationality," United Press International (UPI), H. Ullman, 2021, https://www.upi.com/Top_News/Voices/2021/06/30/Harlan-Ullman-American-politics-rational/3071624717263/
178. "UN failed to protect civilians in South Sudan, report finds." The Guardian, P. Wintour, 2016, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/nov/01/un-failed-to-protect-civilians-in-south-sudan-report-finds>
179. "Terrorist Groups in Afghanistan," Congressional Research Service, C. Thomas, 2021, <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/IF10604.pdf>
180. "Why ISIS-K poses a significant security threat in Afghanistan as civilians, troops attempt to flee," CBC Explains, M. Gollom, 2021, <https://www.cbc.ca/news/world/isis-k-afghanistan-taliban-security-threat-1.6153177>
181. "The Fall of Kabul: A Tragedy Worse Than Saigon, a Warning Japan Can't Ignore." Japan-forward.com., Y. Komori, 2021, <https://japan-forward.com/the-fall-of-kabul-a-tragedy-worse-than-saigon-a-warning-japan-cant-ignore/>
182. "Milley and Austin Should Resign," National Review: National Security and Defense, By The NR Editors, 2021, <https://www.nationalreview.com/2021/08/milley-and-austin-should-resign/>
183. "The Fascinating Afterlife of Peru's Mummies," Smithsonian Journeys Quarterly, C. Heaney, 2015, <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/travel/fascinating-afterlife-perus-mummies-180956319/>
184. "History in Peru," Frommers.com., <https://www.frommers.com/destinations/peru/in-depth/history>
185. "War in Ancient Times," World History Encyclopedia, J.J.Mark, 2009, <https://www.worldhistory.org/war/>
186. "Sunni v Shia: why the conflict is more political than religious," The Guardian, I. Black, 2015, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2015/apr/05/sunni-shia-why-conflict-more-political-than-religious-sectarian-middle-east>
187. "Islam's Sunni-Shia Divide, Explained The split between the two main sects within Islam goes back some 1,400 years," History.com., S. Pruitt, 2019, <https://www.history.com/news/sunni-shia-divide-islam-muslim>
188. "Planetary Fact Sheet - Ratio to Earth Values," NASA, Dr. D.R. Williams, 2019, https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/planetary/factsheet/planet_table_ratio.html
189. "Mysterious Costa Rica Stone Spheres Granted World Heritage status," The Tico Times, 2014, <https://ticotimes.net/2014/06/23/mysterious-stone-spheres-granted-unesco-world-heritage-status>
190. "Mesopotamian Warfare: The Sumerians, Akkadians and Babylonians," History on the Net, <https://www.historyonthenet.com/mesopotamian-warfare-the-sumerians-akkadians-and-babylonians>
191. "Chronology of Mesopotamia," https://piccionepeople.cofc.edu/graphics/mesop_chronol.html
192. Book of Exodus
193. Book of Numbers

-
194. "The Holy of Holies in the Tabernacle," Learn Religions.com.J. Zavada, 2019,
<https://www.learnreligions.com/the-holy-of-holies-700111>
 195. "Sin: Mesopotamian God, Britannica Encyclopedia, By The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2009,
<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Sin-Mesopotamian-god>
 196. "Natural History of Ashkenazi Intelligence," Department of Anthropology: University of Utah, G. Cochran, J.Hardy & H. Harpending, <http://web.mit.edu/fustflum/documents/papers/AshkenazilQ.jbiosocsci.pdf>
 197. "Crusades: Christianity," Encyclopedia Britannica, T.F. Madden.G Dickson & M.W. Baldwin, 2020,
<https://www.britannica.com/event/Crusades>
 198. "Oskar Schindler," Biography.com., 2015, <https://www.biography.com/activist/oskar-schindler#citation>
 199. "Final Solution: Nazi policy," Britannica Encyclopedia, <https://www.britannica.com/event/Final-Solution>
 200. "The tragically powerful story behind the lone German who refused to give Hitler the Nazi salute," Insider, Businessinsider.com., A. Macias, 2015,
<https://www.businessinsider.com/the-lone-german-man-who-refused-to-give-hitler-the-nazi-salute-2015-6>
 201. "August Landmesser," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/August_Landmesser
 202. "Enhancing the experience of music worldwide.," <https://www.musixmatch.com/>
 203. "War Is Old Men Talking and Young Men Dying:The Story of Dennis Lee Klimpke," University of Wisconsin-Eau Claire, G. M. Cropsey, 2017,
https://minds.wisconsin.edu/bitstream/handle/1793/76840/Cropsey_Garrett_2017%20Spring_Hist489.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y
 204. "'What really draws men to war?' Masculinity and conflict in the work of Tim Hetherington, London School of Economics and Political Science Blog, D. Cullen, 2019,
<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/gender/2019/04/23/what-really-draws-men-to-war/>
 205. "MSRC's David Rudd consulted: Why modern soldiers are more susceptible to suicide", " Military Suicide Research Consortium (MSRC), B. Briggs,
<https://msrc.fsu.edu/news/msrcs-david-rudd-consulted-why-modern-soldiers-are-more-susceptible-suicide>
 206. " 13 Assassins," sublikescript.com, https://sublikescript.com/movie/13_Assassins-1436045
 207. "Masculinity and War," The University of Chicago Press Journals, R. B. Ferguson,
<https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/full/10.1086/711622>
 208. "How the 'Horse Soldiers' helped liberate Afghanistan from the Taliban 18 years ago," Militarytimes.com., D.S. Correll, 2019,
<https://www.militarytimes.com/news/your-military/2019/10/18/how-the-horse-soldiers-helped-liberate-afghanistan-from-the-taliban-18-years-ago/>
 209. "Doolittle Raid on Japan 78 Years Ago Buoyed American Spirits," US Department of Defense, D. Vergun, 2020,
<https://www.defense.gov/Explore/Features/story/Article/2148287/doolittle-raid-on-japan-78-years-ago-buoyed-american-spirits/>
 210. "Zeus and his Fight with Typhon," greek-gods.info.,
<https://www.greek-gods.info/greek-gods/zeus/stories/zeus-typhoon/>
 211. "John Rambo: Sir, do we get to win this time? Trautman: This time it's up to you." ~First Blood Part 2
 212. "The War in Afghanistan Was a Scam: The 20-year conflict was a boon to the military-industrial complex, at the cost of untold lives.," The New Republic (TNR), J. Linkins, 2021,
<https://newrepublic.com/article/163323/afghanistan-war-military-industrial-complex-scam>
 213. "One Hundred Eleventh Congress of the United States of America," Govinfo.gov.,
<https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/BILLS-111hr3590enr/pdf/BILLS-111hr3590enr.pdf>
 214. "Axioms of Power," Sf. R. Careaga, 2019
 215. "China vs. the World: IQ as a Strategic Asset; a graphical comparison," academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/50652106/China_vs_the_World_IQ_as_a_Strategic_Asset_a_graphical_comparison
 216. "Attacks on Asians Highlight New Racial Tensions," The New York Times, G. Shih, 2010,
<https://www.nytimes.com/2010/05/02/us/02sfcrime.html>
 217. "Can U.S. States Declare Bankruptcy?," Investopedia, D. D'souza, 2020,
<https://www.investopedia.com/can-u-s-states-declare-bankruptcy-4843140>

-
218. "U.S. students' academic achievement still lags that of their peers in many other countries," Pew Research Center, D. DeSilver, 2017, <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2017/02/15/u-s-students-internationally-math-science/>
219. "America has been at NATO's helm for 70 years. Can it survive without US leadership?," The World (radio program), C. Woolf, 2019, <https://www.pri.org/stories/2019-04-03/america-has-been-nato-s-helm-70-years-can-it-survive-without-us-leadershi>
[p](#)
220. "MIMS 2+ : Applications and Discussions: A continuing internal dialogue about the use of theMIMS theory with particular application to discussion of Thomas Edison, Business,Mysticism, ConspiracyTheories, Innovation, and Personal Finance Management," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions
221. "The Government Orchestrated and Staged Each of These Mass-Casualty Events," New York Magazine, 2013, <https://nymag.com/news/features/conspiracy-theories/false-flags/>
222. "C.I.A. Admits Government Lied About U.F.O. Sightings," The New York Times, W .J. Broad, 1997, <https://www.nytimes.com/1997/08/03/us/cia-admits-government-lied-about-ufo-sightings.html>
223. "CIA's Role in the Study of UFOs, 1947-90," Studies In Intelligence Vol. 01 No. 1, G.K.Haines, 1997, <https://sgp.fas.org/library/ciaufu.html>
224. "Emperor of Japan," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emperor_of_Japan
225. "FactCheck: Was damage to the ozone layer caused by nuclear testing?" TheJournal.ie., D.Healy-Rae, 2016, <https://www.thejournal.ie/ozone-layer-damage-depletion-nuclear-testing-danny-healy-rae-3057410-Nov2016/>
226. "Mutual assured destruction: Military Science," Britannica Encyclopedia, 2020, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/mutual-assured-destruction>
227. "Demographic Perspectives on Family Change," NCBI, 2011, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK56255/>
228. "Why free speech is under attack from right and left," The Christian Science Monitor, H. Bruinius, 2021, <https://www.csmonitor.com/USA/Politics/2021/0701/Why-free-speech-is-under-attack-from-right-and-left>
229. "United States Events of 2019," Human Rights Watch, hrw.org., 2020, <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2020/country-chapters/united-states>
230. "Most young Americans prefer socialism to capitalism, new report finds," Cnbc.com., K. Elkins, 2018, <https://www.cnn.com/2018/08/14/fewer-than-half-of-young-americans-are-positive-about-capitalism.html>
231. "Public Opinion Review: Americans' Reactions to the Word 'Socialism'," Gallup, F. Newport, 2020, <https://news.gallup.com/opinion/polling-matters/287459/public-opinion-review-americans-word-socialism.aspx>
232. "What You Should Know About The U.S. And Human Rights, ACLU, <https://www.aclu.org/sites/default/files/assets/121013-humanrightsfacts.pdf>
233. Ch 2.6, "The Art of War," L. Giles "Sacred Texts," <https://www.sacred-texts.com/tao/aow/aow01.htm>
234. "The English Works, vol. VIII (The Peloponnesian War Part I)," English Works of Thomas Hobbes, <https://oll.libertyfund.org/title/hobbes-the-english-works-vol-viii-the-peloponnesian-war-part-i>
235. "Did Reagan Win the Cold War? Strategic Insights, Volume III, Issue 8, J. W. Knopf, 2004, https://www.google.com/url?q=https://www.hsd1.org/?view%26did%3D444565&sa=D&source=editors&ust=1631046578775000&usq=AOvVaw3f8H5MsWeEyXPXNJL_GGWk
236. "Stealth War: How China Took Over While America's Elite Slept," Gen. R. Spalding, 2019
237. "China's debt tops 300% of GDP, now 15% of global total: IIF," Reuters, 2019, <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-china-economy-debt/chinas-debt-tops-300-of-gdp-now-15-of-global-total-iif-idUSKCN1UD0KD>
238. "THE "Art Of War" Corpus and Chinese Just War Ethics Past and Present," The Journal of Religious Ethics Vol. 40, No. 3 /JSTOR, P.-Cheung Lo, 2012, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23250704>
239. "Bear Grylls: The Island, Season 2
240. "Loose Nukes," Council on Foreign Relations/cfr.org., 2006, <https://www.cfr.org/background/loose-nukes>
241. "Loose Nukes: Black Market Sales of Nuclear Weapons and Material in Russia," NTI- Nuclear Threat Initiative, S. Manning, 1997, <https://www.nti.org/analysis/articles/loose-nukes-black-market-sales-nuclear-weapons-and-material-russia/>

-
242. "The Baby Boom," Khan Academy/khanacademy.org.,
<https://www.khanacademy.org/humanities/us-history/postwarera/postwar-era/a/the-baby-boom>
243. "MIMS & Shi," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi
244. "Energetic Technologies," Presentation by Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1j9pBwAonLP_qH5TYoQ-EOm23UI93sKW6gN1pM1Bipw/edit#slide=id.p
245. De means "inner power" See: "Original Tao," H. Roth, 1999
246. See: "The 48 Laws of Power," R. Greene, 1998
247. "Interpreting the influence of liquid temperature on cavitation collapse intensity through bubble dynamic analysis." Science Direct/Ultrasonics Sonochemistry Volume 69, K. Peng et al., 2020,
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1350417720303229>
248. Six Secret Teachings ch6., ctext.org
249. "Addendum 2: Megafauna Extinction Events Update to the Thunderbolt Extinction Model; the Surprising truth of the Younger Dryas Event that Changes Everything," Research Gate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything
250. "Hubris: The Inside Story of Spin, Scandal, and the Selling," M. Isikoff & D. Corn, 2006
251. "ISIS behead five Kurdish fighters, including three women, whose severed heads are then shared online by terror fanatics, Daily Mail.com., Reuters & D. Gayle, 2014,
<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2777067/ISIS-behead-five-Kurdish-fighters-including-three-women-severed-heads-shared-online-terror-fanatics.html>
252. "Army's first female infantry officer blasts lower standards for women," New York Post, E. Jacobs, 2021,
<https://nypost.com/2021/05/11/armys-first-female-infantry-officer-blasts-lower-standards/>
253. "The Pentagon's Law of War Manual: Part one," World Socialist Web Site/wsws.org., T. Carter, 2015,
<https://www.wsws.org/en/articles/2015/11/03/laws-n03.html>
254. "Pentagon Report Points to US Preparations for Total War, Debt to Success System/dtss.us/blog, 2018,
<https://www.dtss.us/blog/pentagon-report-points-to-us-preparations-for-total-war/>
255. "Deceiving the Sky," B. Gertz, 2019
256. 两虎相争，必有一伤 liǎng hǔ xiāng zhēng , bì yǒu yī shāng "if two tigers fight, one must get injured; if you start a war, someone is bound to get hurt" <http://www.standardmandarin.com/>
257. "\$3 trillion and counting- global players eyeing Afghanistan's vast mineral reserves," MSN.com., /India Today, S. Sharma, 2021,
<https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/other/3-trillion-and-counting-global-players-eyeing-afghanistans-vast-mineral-reserves/ar-AANOUrZ>
258. "Ever Given' Ship That Blocked Suez Canal In March Crosses Waterway Again," Republicworld.com., A. Varma, 2021,
<https://www.republicworld.com/world-news/africa/ever-given-ship-that-blocked-suez-canal-in-march-crosses-waterway-again.html>
259. "The Lakes of The Ubari (Awbari) Sand Sea of Fezzan," Temehu.com.,
https://www.temehu.com/Cities_sites/Gabroun.htm
260. "Americans Weary Of Thankless Mideast Nation-Building," Investor's Business Daily,
<https://www.investors.com/politics/commentary/americans-tired-of-mideast-nationbuilding/>
261. "Iranian Revolution [1978–1979]," Britannica Encyclopedia, J. Afary, 2021,
<https://www.britannica.com/event/Iranian-Revolution>
262. "Cyberspace- The Fifth Operational Domain," Ida.org., General L.D. Welch, 2011,
<https://www.ida.org/-/media/feature/publications/2/20/2011-cyberspace---the-fifth-operational-domain/2011-cyberspace---the-fifth-operational-domain.ashx>
263. "Space, Cyber and Changing Notions of War," Smallwarsjournal.com., J. Drew, 2017,
<https://smallwarsjournal.com/jrnl/art/space-cyber-and-changing-notions-of-war>
264. "Nikola Tesla Papers Envisioned Renewable Energy For A Better World," Racing Nellie Bly/racingnelliebly.com., 2017, <https://racingnelliebly.com/weirdscience/nikola-tesla-papers-envisioned-renewable-energy/>

-
265. "Magnetic Universe Theory A Top-Down Review of Phases of Magnetic Theory Development, with accompanying historiography and comparison with Unified/Aether Field Theories including EPEMC," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC
266. "After Destroying American Energy Production, Biden Begs OPEC to Pump More Oil," Townhall.com., K. Pavlich, 2021,
<https://townhall.com/tipsheet/katiepavlich/2021/08/11/after-canceling-the-keystone-pipeline-biden-begs-opec-for-more-oil-n2593981>
267. "Pathetic and embarrassing': Biden asks OPEC to up oil output while limiting U.S. energy production," The Washington Times, J. Mordock, 2021,
<https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2021/aug/11/joe-biden-asks-opec-oil-output-while-limiting-us-e/>
268. "Domestic Violence and the LGBTQ Community," nadv.org., 2018,
<https://ncadv.org/blog/posts/domestic-violence-and-the-lgbtq-community>
269. "Max Berger Afghanistan war neocons like George W. Bush would like you to know this isn't their fault," nbcnews.com., 2021,
<https://www.nbcnews.com/think/opinion/afghanistan-war-neocons-george-w-bush-would-you-know-isn-ncna1277267>
270. "Responding to the Cosmic Hoax," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/49955630/Responding_to_the_Cosmic_Hoax
271. "Myths of the Cherokee," Extract from the Nineteenth Annual Report of the Bureau of American Ethnology, J. Mooney, 1902, <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/45634/45634-h/45634-h.htm#s108>
272. "Gaia hypothesis,"
<https://courses.seas.harvard.edu/climate/eli/Courses/EPS281r/Sources/Gaia/Gaia-hypothesis-wikipedia.pdf>
273. See the writings of Liu Yiming, such as "The Book of Balance and Harmony" transl. By T. Cleary
274. "Trigram Law (Bagua Dharma) Short document, single page reference," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2015,
https://www.academia.edu/50804985/Trigram_Law_Bagua_Dharma_Short_document_single_page_reference
275. "Six Conformation Diagnosis in Context: The Six Cosmic Qi (liu qi) and the Six Stages of Qi Transformation (liu jing)," ClassicalChinesemedicine.org., H. Fruehauf, 2009,
<https://classicalchinesemedicine.org/six-conformation-diagnosis-in-context-the-six-cosmic-qi-liu-qi-and-the-six-stages-of-qi-transformation-liu-jing/>
276. "Borg," Memory Alpha, <https://memory-alpha.fandom.com/wiki/Borg>
277. "Boxing Out Hyper-Masculinity," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019,
https://www.academia.edu/40245389/Boxing_Out_Hyper_Masculinity
278. "NASA Is Trying to Figure Out How to Kill the International Space Station Whose job is it to take out the trash when the ISS is retired?" Futurism.com., <https://futurism.com/nasa-trying-kill-international-space-station>
279. "US Military Plans to Build Factories on the Moon," Interestingengineering.com., F. Lang, 2021,
<https://interestingengineering.com/us-military-plans-to-build-factories-on-the-moon>
280. "U.S. Air Force cadets study idea of Space Force bases on the Moon," Science/science.org., S. Scoles, 2020,
<https://www.science.org/news/2020/07/us-air-force-cadets-study-idea-space-force-bases-moon>
281. "The Creature from Jekyll Island," G. Griffin, 1994
282. "Sure, Social Security's A Ponzi Scheme - But Is It A Sustainable One Or Not?" Forbes, T. Worstall, 2017,
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/timworstall/2017/04/04/sure-social-securitys-a-ponzi-scheme-but-is-it-a-sustainable-one-or-not/?sh=5972d1953ab6>
283. "The Social Security Ponzi Scheme," Elderlawaustin.com., By The Garrett Law Firm, 2020,
<https://elderlawaustin.com/social-security-ponzi-scheme/>
284. "Did Albert Einstein Say World War IV Will be Fought 'With Sticks and Stones'?" Snopes.com., D. Evon, 2018,
<https://www.snopes.com/fact-check/einstein-world-war-iv-sticks-stones/>
285. "Desiderata," Desiderata.com., <https://www.desiderata.com/desiderata.html>